

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research
infrastructure PLUS

Report on Data and ICT needs from Research Challenges (RCs) to be used in Virtual Access (VA)

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Table of content

1	Introduction	7
1.1	Project context	7
1.2	Research infrastructure context	8
1.3	Making data FAIR	9
2	eLTER context	15
2.1	Scientific scope	15
2.2	User scope	18
2.3	Data scope	22
2.4	Infrastructure scope	26
3	Methods	28
3.1	Data requirement collection	28
3.2	ICT Requirement collection	28
4	Results	31
4.1	Data needs from RC science cases	31
4.2	ICT needs from RC science cases	33
5	Mapping of User story to ENVRI-RM	56
6	Next steps	57
6.1	Develop eLTER data products	57
6.2	Make eLTER FAIR	58
6.3	Develop infrastructure components	60
7	References	62
8	Annexes	64
8.1	Description of eLTER PLUS Science Cases	64
8.2	Data Requirements by eLTER PLUS Science Cases	68
8.3	ICT Requirements Interview template Data users	76
8.4	ICT Requirements Interview template Data providers	79
8.5	ICT Requirements List of User Stories	81
8.6	ICT Requirements Mapping to ENVRI-RM	94

Summary

Progress in understanding, managing, and securing current and future ecosystem functions and services is challenged by fragmented and dispersed ecosystem research. As the topic is often approached using narrow disciplinary perspectives, a holistic understanding of complex eco- and socio-ecological systems is hampered and prevented. The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) evaluated the emerging European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems Research Infrastructure (eLTER RI)¹ as having high potential for addressing this issue in the ecosystem and biodiversity domain, thereby closing this gap in the European RI landscape.

The primary objective of eLTER PLUS is to open and expand the research capacities and impact of eLTER by engaging current and new users and facilitating cross- and transdisciplinary research, exemplified in eLTER Site and Platform design and the RI's Standard Observation framework. eLTER PLUS will execute a performance test of the emerging RI and assess and strengthen its operations in real time. Within the eLTER PLUS project an assessment of the most up-to-date user requirements was performed in order to provide input for the development of the eLTER Information System and to assist in defining topic service areas for the emerging eLTER RI. We compared these requirements with earlier assessments conducted within the eLTER project (e.g. Oggioni et al., 2015; Watkins et al., 2015).

The current document provides an overview of the data and Information and Communications Technology (ICT) requirements of the users emerging from the sciences cases in the eLTER PLUS project (see paragraph 3.1 and 3.2 for the description of the users identified for defining user requirements). These findings are used to derive functional (i.e. the behaviour of essential features of the system) and non-functional (i.e. the general characteristics of the system) requirements for the Information Technology (IT) infrastructure and services, as well as to focus on data needs for large-scale analyses. The content will be used to design and further develop IT components in WP11. This document is a first iteration of user requirements and their implications for eLTER ICT development presenting high-level user stories collected following a user centric approach. As development proceeds during the project and research advances, it will certainly be a living document in the sense that acquired knowledge will inform and influence further iterations of development, for instance by updating the proposed use cases in cooperation with stakeholders.

¹ See <https://www.lter-europe.net/elter-esfri>

Abbreviations

CDN	Central data node
DEIMS-SDR	Dynamic Ecological Information Management System – Site and Dataset Registry
DIP	Data Integration Platform
eLTER	
EML	Ecological Metadata Language
ENVRI-RM	ENVRI-Reference Model
Envthes	Environmental thesaurus
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-Useable
GEO	Group of Earth Observations
GEOSS	GEO System of Systems
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for spatial information in Europe
INSPIRE EF	INSPIRE Environmental Monitoring Facility
ISO	International Standardisation Organisation
IT	Information Technology
MD	Metadata
NC	National LTER network coordinator
NRI	National research infrastructure
O&M	Observation & Measurements
OGC SOS	OGC Sensor Observation Service
PN	Partner data node
RA	Remote Access
RC	Research challenge
RI	Research infrastructure
SC	Science case
SO	Standard observations
SPC	Site and platform coordinator
TA	Transnational Access
TSA	Topic service area
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work package
WUE	Water use efficiency

1 Introduction

The eLTER PLUS project is an advanced communities project that drives the development of the eLTER community toward the establishment of a formal RI. The sister eLTER Preparatory Phase Project (eLTER PPP) is integrating the assessment of user requirements and piloting of services for consideration within the development of an eLTER ESFRI. The data and ICT requirements described in this report should be viewed in this context.

1.1 Project context

Progress in understanding, managing, and securing current and future ecosystem functions and services is challenged by fragmented and dispersed ecosystem research. As the topic is often approached using narrow disciplinary perspectives, a holistic understanding of complex eco- and socio-ecological systems is hampered and sometimes prevented. The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) evaluated the emerging European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems Research Infrastructure (eLTER RI)² as having high potential for addressing this issue in the ecosystem and biodiversity domain, thereby closing this gap in the European RI landscape.

The primary objective of eLTER PLUS is to open and expand the research capacities and impact of eLTER by engaging current and new users and facilitating cross- and transdisciplinary research, exemplified in eLTER Site and Platform design and the RI's Standard Observation framework. eLTER PLUS will execute a performance test of the emerging RI and assess and strengthen its operations in real time.

It will further advance community building and provisioning of services as pursued by the H2020-funded eLTER INFRAIA Starting Community project and related projects. Its focus is making intensive use of 35 selected sites and platforms in terrestrial, freshwater, and coastal ecosystems, combined with observational data from an additional 50 sites, for studying ecosystem and socio-ecological responses to globally-relevant environmental challenges in terms of ecosystem integrity and ecosystem services. Its Whole-Systems approach will derive meaningful scientific and policy relevant information via co-designed, transdisciplinary research in collaboration with diverse stakeholders at local, regional and EU-scales. Concerted actions also focus on collaboration with peer RIs to maximize synergies, increase efficiencies and catalyse holistic understanding of ecosystem function, and on development of virtual laboratories where in-situ site data are linked with other data sources, e.g. Copernicus.

The eLTER PLUS project works towards a further integration of existing services for the LTER community and the eLTER RI, linking requirements not only from the current project but addressing a wider research infrastructure needs. Focusing on the requirements both in terms of data and service needs is a core task within the project.

² See <https://www.lter-europe.net/elter-esfri>

Figure 1 provides an overview of the project design, showing the interlinkages between the different activities, which are fed by a number of processes internal of, and external to, the current project. The right side of the figure highlights the input by scientific and other user communities driving exemplary thematic Science Cases (SCs). The project outcomes, related to communities' requirements and developments feeds into the eLTER ESFRI process, as represented on the left side of Figure 1. Synthesis and networking activities (e.g. WP 2, 3, 5, and 6) link project outcomes, related communities' requirements and the development of eLTER Information Clusters (WP 4), as shown in the top part, within the eLTER PLUS project. These activities occur in parallel to a strategically driven site selection process based on the existing eLTER site pool for the use of the site infrastructure for Transnational Access (TA) and Remote Access (RA) research and data-use opportunities, as well as providing access to data and services from these sites via Virtual Access (VA).

Figure 1: The core concept of eLTER PLUS (Source: eLTER PLUS Proposal)

For the selected science cases, a Whole System Approach is realized by cross-theme collaboration within WP8 (site/platform scale) and WP9 (catchment scale). The work packages WP10 and WP11 aim to translate user requirements and research products across themes into tool and data product specifications and perform service/tools piloting and implementation. The current report aims to review existing user requirements and update them by collecting current needs as expressed by an extended user community.

1.2 Research infrastructure context

The emerging eLTER RI forms part of a family of environmental RIs, each designed to provide a range of services for the research communities within Europe and globally. As eLTER aspires to a *Whole Systems Approach* to environmental research, a key requirement is the use of other complementary RI services and data to enable cross-disciplinary approaches. This implicitly needs to be considered when analysing and describing the requirements for services within the development of the eLTER RI. In particular, the development of analytical

workflow and data access services will often require access to more than one RI to be effective for the research communities served. In this context, the development of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)³ services need to be considered to enable the integration of services across existing RIs and e-infrastructures, as well as developing those services specifically provided by the emerging eLTER RI.

Figure 2: The percentage relevance of different environmental RIs to societal and environmental Grand Challenges. eLTER interacts with other RIs to work across these challenges (Source: ENVRI-PLUS).

eLTER forms a key nexus between investigation of environmental parameters and their association with environmental resource management and use across European landscapes, as shown in Figure 2. In summary, eLTER will collaborate with other RIs to address Grand Challenges through a set of harmonised and FAIR data and ICT services.

1.3 Making data FAIR

Data communication and management are key issues of interdisciplinary research projects and related research infrastructures. The overall success depends on the well-organized management and exchange of data between involved partners. Practices facilitating the acquisition, provision, integration, and sharing of heterogeneous digital resources within a scientific and non-scientific multiuser (distributed) environment must:

- enable easily locatable data, and its reuse

³ see <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

- reflect the partners and stakeholders organizational and/or institutional constraints and needs in terms of data management and sharing
- consider both data processing (research) and data security requirements
- help to discover datasets to be stored and used for only a temporary, predefined period
- ensure the long-term archiving of the datasets
- enhance management and documentation of data provenance
- be flexible and upgradable
- meet common data and metadata standards to be compatible with other data management systems
- meet common data transfer protocols and mechanisms for project data and metadata
- support the international vision for opening access to research data

In recent years, a number of relevant initiatives like the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) emerged aiming to provide general guidelines to encourage open data by assisting in the implementation of practices listed above. Starting with defining levels of open data (Berners-Lee, 2006), the definition of “open data” is common across the different initiatives as a core principle and prerequisite for open data and open science. The key features for openness are (Open Knowledge Foundation, 2019):

- **Availability and Access:** The data must be available as a whole and for a reasonable reproduction cost, preferably accessible via the internet. The data must also be available in a convenient and modifiable form.
- **Re-use and Redistribution:** The data must be provided under terms that permit re-use and redistribution including allowing for aggregation with other datasets.
- **Universal Participation:** Every potential user must be able to use, re-use and redistribute the data - there should be no discrimination regarding fields of endeavour or regarding persons or groups. As an example, ‘non-commercial’ restrictions that would prevent ‘commercial’ use, or restrictions of use for certain purposes (e.g. only in education) are not allowed.

Besides a set of IT services to assure the accessibility of data, the openness revolution implies that research enterprises operating at any level (from local projects to large research infrastructure) will adopt data policies and promote the use of licences which reduce the restrictions applied to the data. The European Commission encourages all research funded in Horizon 2020 to be open, enabling anybody to freely access scientific publications and to allow them to opportunity to validate published results. Open access means that research results and research data are stored in a research data repository so that it is possible to obtain, mine, exploit, reproduce, and disseminate the data, free of charge. Examples of research data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, handwritten notes, observations resulting from field work, survey results, interview recordings, and images. However, reuse of data also requires data to be interoperable, accessible, and sufficiently documented. Therefore, data provision itself should follow the FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), meaning that all research data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. These principles refer to data (or any digital object), metadata (information about that digital object), and infrastructures.

Figure 3: The FAIR Data Object contains not only data, but also identifiers, standards and metadata, which enable reuse of the data as well as citation and provenance tracking and citation. Figure taken from <https://github.com/FAIR-Data-EG/Action-Plan/issues/3>

The resulting key principles relevant in the eLTER PLUS context are the FAIR principles defined by FORCE11⁴, as well as the Open Science and Open Data Principles defined by the European Commission. Based on these principles, eLTER PLUS aims to extend the eLTER Information System⁵ to support the workflows and scientific analyses of eLTER data provided by a wide range of eLTER sites. This will be achieved taking into account (i) the rapidly changing landscape of data sharing in Europe and worldwide, and (ii) new requirements determined within the evolving eLTER RI as a contributing data infrastructure. The implementation of the data management infrastructure builds on the work done in the previous eLTER (H2020) project and takes into account such developments as those presented in the “Results” chapter.

1.3.1 Persistent identification

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are a cornerstone in the FAIR Ecosystem, as well-managed and controlled use of identifiers enable data lifecycle management, scientific reproducibility, as well as data citation. Publication of persistent identifiers is always linked to trustworthy services and governance. Data citation, provenance tracking, and credit for data providers have been

⁴ see <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

⁵ see <https://data.lter-europe.net>

identified as important needs. As the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and other ESFRIs are developing towards a FAIR data environment, shared practices and policies are emerging. The eLTER community will follow these developments closely to ensure interoperability and compatibility.

Services that offer PID resolvers are considered most stable. Open protocols, transparent management and interoperability are key factors when choosing PID solutions for different use cases. Persistent identifiers should be offered or supported for datasets, sites, platforms, variables, instruments and possibly other RI components, like protocols, code and workflows. Where external PIDs are available they should be supported. Regarding organisations and researchers, existing PIDs should be used. PID corruption and content drift should be mitigated.

1.3.2 Data and metadata interoperability

Semantic interoperability⁶ is the ability of computer systems to exchange data with unambiguous, shared meaning of the content, which is shared without being corrupted or lost. This can be done in many ways with changing degrees of complexity and machine actionability. The simplest way might be using a shared list of values or codes (controlled vocabulary) or even formats like ISO codes for language or time stamps in the dataset or metadata. Even these kinds of lists or standards need management and version control to be sustainable over time.

Syntactic interoperability is a prerequisite to semantics. It involves a common data format and common protocol to structure any data so that the information provided will be machine-processable. It also allows detection of syntactic errors, which must be resolved. However, where accurate translation of syntaxes is possible, systems using different syntaxes may also interoperate accurately. This requirement is addressed by the I1 component of the FAIR Guiding Principles emphasizing the use of a knowledge representation language which is formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable like RDF and OWL.

Semantic interoperability is referred to in the FAIR principles I2 and I3. I2 specifies that metadata should use terms and concepts from FAIR vocabularies. I3 determines that metadata should contain qualified references as defined in (meta)data models (ontologies) to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data.

Semantics is expressed in many ways within research data and metadata. More advanced, complex solutions with high machine actionability are in use thanks to rich but well-structured descriptions of the relations between concepts. Relevant work has been done and is ongoing, like in RDA I-ADOPT⁷. The goal of this working group is to develop an interoperability framework for observable property descriptions, which will foster interoperability between cross-domain semantic artefacts by providing a common method to systematically express or represent observable properties.

⁶ See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Semantic_interoperability, retrieved May 17th, 2018

⁷ See <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/interoperable-descriptions-observable-property-terminology-wg-i-adopt-wg/wiki/i-adopt-0>

There are still many challenges regarding semantic interoperability due to different maturity levels and varying needs and approaches across different research domains. In addition, the terminology of semantics used varies with regard to the use of terms like “vocabulary” or “ontology”. To bridge this ambiguity, we use the term *Semantic Artefact* for all various solutions that code for semantics (see Figure 4) in ways that support both machines and human end-users. The FAIRsFAIR project recently produced a “1st set of Recommendations for FAIR Semantics” where the term “semantic artefact” was defined as “a machine-actionable and -readable formalisation of a conceptualisation enabling sharing and reuse by humans and machines. These artefacts may have a broad range of formalisation, from a loose set of terms, taxonomies, thesauri to higher-order logics. Moreover, semantic artefacts are serialised using a variety of digital representation formats, e.g., RDF Turtle, OWL-RDF, XML, JSON-LD.”⁸

Figure 4: Semantic artefact spectrum. Derived from Leo Obrst, 2010. This figure is from the “1st set of Recommendations for FAIR Semantics” 2020 (Source: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3707985>)

On a conceptual level many values in the eLTER metadata could be viewed through this lens: as sites, instruments or variables turn into metadata elements in the eLTER metadata, they should be managed as semantic artefacts offering machine access to structured data, as machine readable and interoperable as possible. Common persistent identifiers should be used across the eLTER universe for as many elements as possible, and the management of these should support FAIR principles.

1.3.3 Data reusability and provenance

As outlined in FAIR principle R1.2, one key ingredient for providing reusable data is the publication of relevant provenance information. Traditionally described in free-text form using

⁸ See <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3707985>

dedicated metadata elements such as “*dcterms:provenance*”, this type of metadata provides information about the genesis of the resource at hand, including used sources, applied processes and responsible agents, with the aim to increase its trustworthiness. Large-scale data integration scenarios such as envisioned in the concept of the EOSC, however, have raised the requirements for provenance descriptions regarding their machine-processability. This has led to the establishment of more advanced concepts for describing provenance in more structured, machine-readable form and specifications such as PROV-DM⁹, which represent a commonly agreed, customizable standard in this regard. As their designation implies, long-term ecological research data are often composed of contributions spanning multiple years to multiple decades, collected via constantly updated instruments and processes. This raises special requirements for related provenance information, which should ideally cover at least the most important aspects of the underlying contributions in this regard, providing re-users with crucial information about how they can be integrated. Modular provenance descriptions, such as those enabled via PROV-DM, would play an important role in such scenarios, where individual provenance traces can be combined into coherent provenance descriptions published alongside the respective integrated data products.

1.3.4 Aim of the document

Within the eLTER PLUS project a collection of the updated user requirements was performed in order to provide an input for the development of the eLTER Information System of the emerging eLTER RI. These requirements were also checked against earlier developments within eLTER (e.g. Oggioni et al., 2015; Watkins et al., 2015).

The current document provides an overview of the data and ICT requirements of the users resulting from the science cases in the eLTER PLUS project (see paragraph 3.1 and 3.2 for the description of the users identified for gathering of requirements). These collections are used to derive functional (i.e. the behaviour of essential features of the system) and non-functional (i.e. the general characteristics of the system) requirements for the IT infrastructure and services, as well as to focus the data needs for large-scale analysis. The content will be used to design and further develop IT components in WP11. This document is a first iteration of the requirement analysis process presenting high-level user stories derived following a user centric approach. As development proceeds during the project and research advances, it will certainly be a living document in the sense that acquired knowledge will inform and influence the development of the document and the processes it describes, for instance by updating the proposed use cases in cooperation with the stakeholders.

The document is structured according to data needs derived from the science cases and the related ICT requirements. Chapter “*eLTER context*” (see chapter 2) describes the context of the project in terms of stakeholders as well as scientific topics to be addressed. Chapter “*Methods*” (see chapter 3) describes the methods applied to derive the requirements. Chapter “*Results*” (see chapter 4) summarises the results of the requirement collection. Chapter “*Next steps*” (see chapter 6) provides recommendations for the system development.

⁹ See <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>

2 eLTER context

2.1 Scientific scope

An important part of the eLTER PLUS project is to improve the key infrastructure services of the LTER networks over the coming years. A key objective of this project is to use existing LTER data to address four topical scientific Research Challenges (RC), for example the impact of drought on ecosystem resilience (see Annex 8.1). eLTER PLUS aims for a unique holistic approach addressing eight case studies (i.e. two science cases for each RC) focusing on biodiversity, biogeochemical, hydrological and socio-ecological systems.

The eLTER PLUS project aims to demonstrate to what extent existing data-rich LTER sites can address overarching RCs, focusing on a wide range of eLTER Sites implementing a “whole systems approach”. Data analysis should as much as possible focus on the use of a common set of eLTER sites (or platforms for socio-ecological questions) enabling and exemplifying the benefit of cross-site analysis.

The eLTER PLUS science cases have been defined addressing key research questions, following the RI Grand Challenges, where eLTER RI will make an important contribution to cross site and cross scale analyses. These research challenges are (a) biodiversity trends and losses (BDL), (b) bio-geochemical processes (BGC), (c) hydrological processes (CWF), and (d) socio-ecological processes (SES) carried out in the project frame.

Based on the science cases, data needs were defined and summarised in the current report. In addition, this information is used to provide input in the selection and definition of the eLTER Standard Observations (see e.g. Mollenhauer et al. 2018) within the eLTER PLUS project.

2.1.1 Biodiversity loss

High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change (Task 8.1)

The main aims of this task are to a) investigate long-term trends in biodiversity, b) identify stressors driving these long-term changes and c) identify indicators for characterising short-term variability as, for example, in response to extreme events. For this, we make use of a relevant subset of data-rich eLTER Sites to quantify long-term trends and short-term variability in biodiversity and relate both to changes in abiotic variables and socio-ecological parameters. Accordingly, data-rich sites with regard to biodiversity and accompanying environmental (driver) data have been identified and suitable data requested. One crucial point will be an appropriate data format. For the biodiversity data, such a format has recently been developed and sent to the data providers.

Representativeness towards pan-European biodiversity pressures and trends (Task 9.1)

The main aim of this task is to compare long-term trends and drivers of biodiversity based on a) small sample sizes, b) high resolution eLTER data with large sample sizes, and c) low resolution non-eLTER data (based on space-for-time substitution) at a pan European scale. For this, we make use of an already existing compilation of 161 biodiversity time series mainly from European eLTER Sites (Pilotto et al. 2020). We will add further datasets to be provided

by other eLTER sites and compile large European biodiversity datasets from non-eLTER sources (e.g. Water Framework Directive monitoring data). As for the previous task, an appropriate data format has been developed and will be used in data compilation.

2.1.2 Biogeochemical control of ecosystem functions

Plot scale ecosystem process understanding (Task 8.2)

This task aims to increase process understanding of the impact of climate change and extreme weather events on carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) cycling and feedbacks in a broad range of ecosystems. Data on C and nutrient stocks and fluxes, climate, N deposition and management from eLTER Sites will be analysed. Extreme weather events (e.g. drought) will be characterised. The task will facilitate a) identification of critical environmental thresholds and tipping points in C and N turnover and fluxes across the eLTER spectrum of ecosystems, climate zones and socio-ecological contexts and b) improvement of our understanding of the impact of extreme weather events and climate change on ecosystem processes.

The Water-Climate-GHG Nexus at the pan-European scale (Task 9.2)

This task aims to test and pilot the co-location of eLTER and ICOS RIs to gain new insights into the pan-European water-climate-GHG nexus, better constrain estimates of the pan-European GHG emission and carbon footprint, and develop a complementary mechanistic understanding. Within the task, the water-climate-GHG nexus will scope across eLTER catchments using the DEIMS metadata, measured, and modelled data. Second, a catchment-scale conceptual model of the water-climate-GHG nexus will be elaborated to better constrain estimates of the pan-European GHG emission and carbon footprint and add a complementary mechanistic understanding to ICOS measurements. This will be achieved through a literature review identifying current approaches to site-scale modelling of the water-climate-GHG nexus that will then be used in a workshop with invited experts from eLTER/ICOS RIs, leaders of relevant Tasks in the project, and external researchers.

2.1.3 Climate-Water-Food nexus

The availability of water resources contributes substantially to maintaining ecosystem integrity, securing food production, and sustaining other ecosystem services. Climate change is expected to increase extreme events such as droughts and heat waves that will affect water availability and increase water demand for irrigation, particularly in arid and semi-arid areas. In addition, increased occurrence of dry spells or high intensity rainfall events have the potential to alter agricultural systems across Europe in terms of land use and management.

The intensification of water use is expected to significantly affect the global water cycle resources, both in quality and quantity across the pan-European domain. eLTER PLUS has the unique capacity to generate continental scale, continuous data products of states and fluxes of the biophysical systems that will enable the application of multi-scale modelling approaches to assess the impact of extreme events (droughts and high intensity rainfall) on ecosystem services, including services that sustain food production, and will facilitate formulation of design adaptation strategies to sustain ecosystem services.

Knowledge on the impacts of drought events on ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE), resilience, and the relationships between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience are of major interest for predicting ecosystem functions and services. Key variables that control WUE and reflect drought stress (several regional drought events) are selected for the site-specific analysis using an integrated numerical model. The integrated model calculates WUE and simulates a climate series of at least 30 years in order to (1) assess the impact of drought events on the WUE of ecosystems, (2) analyse the resilience of the ecosystems with respect to their ability to recover from single and multiple droughts, (3) understand the relationship between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity, and ecosystem resilience and develop mitigation measures for drought adverse impacts, and (4) assess strengths and weaknesses of the RI-design for deriving resilience indicators.

Further, eLTER network data is used to validate a pan-European scale terrestrial ecosystem model and to analyse the impact of climate extremes on water-related ecosystem services. The model simulates hydrological and ecosystem fluxes over a period of 30 years. The terrestrial ecosystem model TerrSysMP (TSMP) operates at a 3 km resolution for the European continent. Climatic forcing is obtained from disaggregation of large-scale atmospheric reanalyses. Remotely sensed time series of several satellite products such as SMOS, SMAP, and Copernicus Hub services validate the terrestrial ecosystem model. The data driven model framework provides reanalysis data of 30 years to eLTER sites constrained by model and observation data. The analysis will demonstrate the concept of ecosystem reanalysis for soil moisture time series, and the assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the current eLTER network design regarding the impact of climate extremes on water-related ecosystem services.

2.1.4 Socio-ecological systems

Socio-ecological analysis of stakeholder defined local and regional environmental challenges (Task 8.4)

This task studies the interactions between socio-ecological states and changes (e.g. land use, resource use, and demography) and extreme events in order to improve understanding of socio-ecological resilience, socioeconomic adaptation, and extreme event mitigation mechanisms. Essential socio-ecological variables necessary for characterizing these relations will be identified and long-term monitoring of the identified variables will be initiated (in coordination with task 10.1.4). In coordination with task 9.4, efficacy of, and gaps in, policies addressing extreme events will be examined. Researchers will define, in consultation with local stakeholders (i.e. resource managers, farmers, tourism operators, and environmental organisations), the region's most pressing extreme events related to land use and resource management issues and use the socio-ecological research framework (Haberl et al. 2006) to characterise these events in terms of interactions between social and ecosystem variables, emphasising social “presses and pulses” on the ecosystem, ecosystem response, and resultant changes in the provision of ecosystem services (Collins et al. 2011). The strengths and weaknesses of the RI-design and associated selection of essential socio-ecological variables will be assessed to determine their utility for characterizing regional and local

resilience to extreme events and to refine long-term data needs for the study of socio-ecological systems.

Assessment of the value of eLTER for European-scale environmental policy (Task 9.4)

The objectives of task 9.4 are to exemplify the value of eLTER research for European environmental policies through the study of aggregate knowledge derived from multiple local/regional scale studies and to examine the relevance of local context on the efficacy of policy implementation. Intrinsic in the experimental design is simultaneous research *for* policy (i.e. how is policy performing with regard to local resilience and how can it be improved) and *of* policy (i.e. how can we better understand the policy process). Specific policy challenges and focal variables will be adopted following a critical assessment of interim results from task 8.4, and the relevant policies will be identified at the local to EU scales. Looking across five pilot LTSE case studies, the efficacy of policies will be assessed using local and regional context as independent variables. The interaction between policies and essential socio-ecological variables will also be explored. Information for each case study will be collected through stakeholder interviews, questionnaires, and historical research.

2.2 User scope

2.2.1 General RI level stakeholders

The emerging eLTER RI evolves towards societal relevance by enhancing a network of sites across Europe which monitor abiotic, biotic and (increasingly) socio-ecological components of the coupled socio-ecological system. In the eLTER H2020 project a report was compiled (Krauze et. al., 2018) focusing on understanding the context, challenges and opportunities arising from the interaction between societal stakeholders and researchers. This resulted in a Best Practice Guide for site managers and national network coordinators at local, sub-national and national levels. Having these interactions in mind, a first brainstorming of relevant stakeholder groups was done within WP2 of the eLTER PLUS project. However, the listing of stakeholders is not complete and will need further revisions throughout the process of implementing the research infrastructure in the coming years. In parallel, under WP7 of the eLTER PPP project, a more comprehensive stakeholder assessment was undertaken, which was comprised of several steps: 1) initial mapping of stakeholder categories, 2) analysis and prioritization of stakeholder relationships within each category, and 3) inventory of existing stakeholder contacts and communication channels. The ultimate goal of this task was the elaboration of a coherent stakeholder engagement strategy and the integration of coordinated approaches and actions across the eLTER PPP and PLUS work plans.

As a result of this work, the relevant stakeholder groups for the eLTER RI could be identified:

- **Research and Research Infrastructure funders**, ranging from national to European, as well as international funding organisations, who are important in the financing and sustainability of the research infrastructure.
- **Researchers and science stakeholders**, being interested in the services (e.g. sites, data, training) of the RI. This group ranges from (for example) individual scientists, research organisations, research networks, and global science initiatives.

- **Government and policy decision-makers**, ranging from European policy makers, European agencies (executive bodies) in the realm of eLTER (e.g. EEA, JRC, contributors to monitoring and conservation directives), to national and regional authorities and policy makers. In addition, global agencies and intergovernmental organisations need to be considered.
- **Business and industry**, users of services of the eLTER RI or who enable innovation and cooperation in terms of observation (e.g. sensors) or information management, as well as environmental (impact) consultants and spatial architects.
- **Civil society and interested members of the public**, ranging from Citizen Science organisations, environmental NGOs, land and forest owners' organisations to the wider public.
- **Peers in environmental research and observation**, like related monitoring and observation networks and organizations in-situ and remote (e.g. UNECE-Working Group on Effects, WMO, JRC, ESA/Copernicus, EIONET) or related research infrastructures in the environmental domain (ICOS, ACTRIS, AnaEE, ENVRI-FAIR, EOSC Services, CESSDA). Within this category, European scale e-infrastructures (e.g. LifeWatch) and e-infrastructure initiatives like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) need to be taken into account as users interacting with the eLTER Information System.
- **Internal stakeholders**, such as the site and platform coordinators (SPC), the site and platform operating institutions or the National LTER networks coordination teams (NC)

Figure 5: Overview on relevant stakeholder groups for the emerging eLTER RI

This list of main stakeholder categories and groups was discussed on several occasions within the eLTER projects, and integrated into relevant strategies and plans, such as the eLTER RI

Strategic Plan, the eLTER Communication Strategy, the eLTER Services Portfolio and others. The list of stakeholders was used in the description process of the “epics” and used to assign and check relevance of the ICT requirements (see Chapter 3.2, which describes the meaning of “epics” and the process by which we obtain them).

2.2.2 (Internal) Stakeholders of the eLTER Information System

Various stakeholders will interact with the eLTER services and the eLTER Information System. We assume that this will be driven by their specific needs and capabilities of the infrastructure. This can range from end users of the data and services to data managers to data stewards on behalf of researchers or data providers. The eLTER requirements collection (see, e.g., Oggioni et al., 2015) resulted in a first version of the identification and description of actors/user roles related to the eLTER Information System. The current work builds on this preceding definition and updates and extends it to reflect the current understanding of the relevant eLTER ICT landscape.

Through this, a number of different relevant actors and user roles can be described:

- **Data provider**, defined as [user] who submits information to the eLTER services. The data might have different eLTER data levels and be more or less harmonised or open. This group reflects a wide range of contributors ranging from single site and platform managers, and individual researchers to research projects or other RIs. Two sub-roles can be distinguished based on their main activities and interaction with the eLTER Information system, (a) *Metadata (MD) provider*, who provides metadata about site, instruments and data, and publishes this to enable linking to distribution; and (b) *Data provider*, who is the provider and distributor of the data. In terms of related activities, a Data provider interacts with the central data infrastructure components (e.g. metadata catalogue, central data repository) providing metadata and data (or links to data). A user account (either personnel or as a group) and related restrictions needs to be defined to be able to document the data.
- **Data user**, defined as [user], e.g. researchers, using data and information from the eLTER network provided through different publishing channels of the eLTER Information System. In this respect, data users can reflect for example research and science stakeholders, government and policy decision-makers, the civil society and interested members of the public or other RIs. Data users are accessing (either directly via data service or by download procedures) the data and can analyse or reuse the data or metadata. Potentially new derived data are generated, which might be of interest for eLTER and need to be published and shared via the eLTER Information System. In terms of related activities, a Data user finds data by the means of metadata, and accesses, evaluates and uses data in analytical workflows. In terms of access, either an authentication is needed or the data can be accessed freely without a user account. Data policies and data usage rules are taken into account by a data user and transferred to the resulting information and data.
- **Data manager**, defined as [user] who is running and managing an installation of a data infrastructure (also defined as data node) contributing to the eLTER Information

System. They are managing all activities needed to run and maintain the data node. Focusing on these two sub-roles can be distinguished based on their activities and interaction with the eLTER Information system: (a) *Data manager of a contributing data node*, who is running and managing a local data infrastructure contributing metadata and data in structured manner to the eLTER Information System; and (b) *Data manager of central data node*, who is providing the infrastructure and the technical requisites for setting up the central data node hosting metadata and data of centralised data workflows.

In terms of related activities, a Data manager manages the accounts and data (including, for example, local data services and data archiving) for the single data node. He also manages the software stack of the data node. A manager account is needed.

- **Service provider**, defined as [user] who runs and manages an installation of a data services contributing to the eLTER Information System. They are managing all activities needed to run and maintain the service. Two sub-roles can be distinguished based on their activities and interaction with the eLTER Information System: (a) *Service management*, reflecting the group providing and prototyping the IT services for the eLTER Information System (e.g. staging area, eLTER CDN, DEIMS-SDR, B2SHARE, eLTER DIP, EnvThes); and (b) *Service support*, reflecting the group supporting users and contributors of the eLTER Information System in the provision of data as well as supporting basic quality control and harmonisation of the data.

In terms of related activities, a Service provider manages the accounts and query distribution to the single data nodes. S/he also manages the data evaluation software. A manager account is needed.

In addition to the roles mentioned above, within the current eLTER PLUS project additional relevant project roles can be defined, which are reflected as Internal Stakeholders:

- **Research challenge leads (RC)**, defined as lead of the research challenges “Biodiversity loss”, “Bio-Geochemical control of ecosystem functions”, “Climate-Water-Food nexus”, and “Socio-Ecological systems”. They coordinate the work of the science cases across the different work packages. This user group also includes the WP leaders for WP8 and WP9.
- **Science case leads and contributors**, defined as lead of, and contributor to, the science cases in the context of WP8 and WP9. This user group reflects the research community. This group defines the data and ICT requirements and are the main users of eLTER data and providers of standardised data products in the project context.
- **Science-technology interface**, defined as interface between the research and ICT community composed of RC leads and technical counterparts in WP10. This group coordinates the data and ICT requirement collection and is the main interface to ICT development (WP11).

During the implementation cycles within the eLTER PLUS project, the relevant roles for the eLTER Information System will continuously be revised and adapted if needed.

2.3 Data scope

The main aim of the emerging eLTER RI and eLTER network is to provide long-term, quality controlled, and harmonised data to analyse and understand ecosystem processes and their vulnerability to environmental changes (e.g. climate change). In order to achieve this goal, observations on the different components of the ecosystem needs to be done. This results in a wide range of data types which needs to be supported.

2.3.1 Data types

eLTER observations are covering a wide range of characteristics of ecosystem and social-ecological components of the environment. This results in many different data types which need to be considered in data management and analysis.

Table 1 lists several examples of relevant data types which are based on the original analysis done by Oggioni et al. 2015 and extended based on interviews within the eLTER PLUS project (see chapter 3). It aims to illustrate the variety of data types and does not cover the full range of possibilities. While developing the different functionalities of the eLTER Information System this variability needs to be taken into account at different levels (e.g., storage, access and visualisation of data).

Also, in terms of data formats, a wide range of input formats needs to be considered. This ranges from single files (e.g., CSV, netCDF) to databases and data services.

Table 1 Examples of relevant data types

Observation type	Description	Features	Observation interval	Procedure	Value type
<i>Single point</i>	single observation at a fixed location by means of a human or instrument (e.g. species function, property or characteristics)	object on which it performs the observation (e.g. the species)	a time instance	observation methodology (e.g. floristic-statistical method) or sensor	numeric, textual, category, count, and boolean
<i>Time series</i>	continuous or repeated observation at a fixed location by means of the human observation (e.g. vegetation or habitat mapping) or an instrument. It can be referred to as a time series collection with a defined frequency or with different sampling times	object on which it performs the observation (e.g. species, population, habitat, etc.)	single point measurement, campaign based or continuous (bigger intervals)	observation methodology (e.g. floristic-statistical method) or sensor	numeric, textual, category, count, and boolean
<i>Profiles</i>	observations collected in varying or discrete depths or altitude (e.g. water column, air column, borehole or drilling of soil or ice), usually by instrument. The location of observations can be identified by the position of the column or located within the column with either relative position	e.g. water column, air column, borehole or drilling of soil or ice, etc.	all observations are collected in the same time instance or in different time instant according with the depth or altitude	sensor	numeric, textual, category, count, boolean, and array.
<i>Trajectories</i>	observations collected continuously along a trajectory (e.g. surface water temperature, transect measurement). The location of observations, also altitude or depth, can be identified by the continuous GPS data logging	e.g. water, air, habitat, etc.	continuous observation	sensor	numeric, textual, category, count, boolean, array, and geometry
<i>Sample based</i>	the observation is done using a sample taken in the field. Sampling could either be a single event or a continuous process. The samples are taken to the lab to be analysed. Data are generated by time delay. The location can be identified by the position where the sample was collected	e.g. water, air, soil, litter, habitat, etc.	Sample collection and laboratory method	numeric, textual, category, count, boolean, and array	
<i>Spatial data</i>	data with a direct or indirect reference to a specific location or geographic area. Dataset is distributed throughout a spatial data format (e.g. shapefile, kmz, GeoJSON, GML, geo-relational database), the data are gathered by features and the geographical representation are of 3 types: point, line and polygon	all environmental areas that can be represented as points, lines, or polygons	single event or repeated	observation methodology, human and sensor	numeric, textual, category, count, and Boolean

Observation type	Description	Features	Observation interval	Procedure	Value type
<i>Coverage data</i>	coverages are used to describe characteristics of real-world phenomena that vary over space and/or time. In practice, the notion of coverages encompasses regular and irregular grids, point clouds, and general meshes. Typical examples are 1-D temperature (time series or vertical profile), 2-D elevation, 2-D precipitation, 2-D imagery, 2-D x/y/t image time series and x/y/z geophysical voxel data, and 4-D x/y/z/t weather data. A coverage contains a set of such values, each associated with one of the elements in a spatial, temporal or spatio-temporal domain	all environmental areas	single event or continuous sampling	observation methodology, human and sensor	numeric, textual, category, count, and boolean
<i>Model results</i>	data resulting from interpolation or modelling results of a real-world phenomenon that covers over space and/or time. Normally this is represented as regular grid (e.g. raster) as a result of an analytical workflow or model output, e.g. temperature surface	all environmental areas	single or continuous process	analytical workflows, modelling procedure	numeric, category
<i>Interview data</i>	data from an interview campaign collecting information (e.g. on land use activities or opinion). In contrast to environmental and ecosystem, GDPR regulation and securing sensitive information needs to be taken into account when personal information is collected. This needs to be taken into account when managing and sharing the data.	e.g. human, land owners, tourists, stakeholders, etc.	single event or repeated	oral or online interviews / surveys	numeric, categorial, free text, boolean
<i>Data publication</i>	Data publication is the process of making information, particularly data generated from research, available to all. Data archiving is the long-term storage of such data and methods. In science, publishing and archiving data is important to preserve scientific information for future research ¹⁰ . Data publication will be used to publish and share dataset from the eLTER network or single eLTER sites	all environmental areas	any	data publication	numeric, categorial, text, count, boolean

¹⁰ See <https://www.nature.com/subjects/data-publication-and-archiving#:~:text=Definition,scientific%20information%20for%20future%20research>

2.3.2 Data levels

For eLTER, different data levels can be defined in the future which also have to be taken into account in terms of data management. Data levels range from raw data to elaborated data products representing the processing status of the data following examples by ICOS¹¹ and TERENO (Kunkel & Sorg, 2016). Data levels could be defined as the following (but will be finalized during the eLTER PLUS project):

- **Level 0** - are defined as **Raw data**, which are values directly obtained by human measurements or automated sensors that have not undergone any transformation. This could include quantitative or qualitative information about physical variables of the environment and may be of various forms, such as images, text files or physical samples. These data are transformed into physical units either directly provided by instruments or converted from engineering units (for example, mV, mA, Ω) to physical units.
- **Level 1** - are defined as **Observation data**, which are unprocessed and have not undergone any refinement or only basic data quality control.
- **Level 2** - are defined as **Cleaned data**, which were subject to quality control procedures (either automatic and/or manual). These data passed the quality control procedures such as routine estimation of timing and sensor calibration and/or statistical/visual inspection to identify outliers and errors in the data. This can also include gap filling of missing data. Level 2 are therefore Cleaned Data that are the final, quality-checked and gap-filled, and published by the local nodes or the central data node (CDN).
- **Level 3** - are defined as **Data Products**, which are derived from quality-controlled data. They require scientific and technical interpretation and may include multi-sensor data, analytical workflows and interpretations, model-based interpretation using also other data to generate the data products. Data products reflect a diversity of products elaborated by scientific communities that rely partly or completely on eLTER lower-level data. eLTER will provide resources to integrate and disseminate Level 3 products.

The data levels are currently in the phase of discussion for the eLTER RI and needs to be further elaborated. Using common workflows and tracking provenance of the data flows and linking data are crucial and needs to be linked to the data. This aspect is also reflected in the functional requirements for the eLTER Information System (see Chapter 4.1).

2.3.3 Data formats

In order to foster data collection for eLTER PLUS, a revision of the eLTER Data Specification¹² was made and published via the web page. The eLTER Data specification reflects a

¹¹ see <https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-services/data-collection/data-levels-quality#toc-data-product-levels>

¹² see https://www.lter-europe.net/projects/PLUS/eLTER_TechDoc_TemplateSpecification.pdf

description of the structure (columns, fields) and content (description) of the data-reporting template. The template consists of core fields (basic reporting) and possible extensions (extended reporting) providing additional fields (e.g. aggregation or quality flags).

2.4 Infrastructure scope

2.4.1 eLTER Information System components

In the development of the eLTER Information System basic components, efforts have been made in the eLTER project (H2020, GA.Nr. 654359) to provide tools for the storage, documentation, discovery, and access of the data covering the main aspects of the data life cycle. These components are the building blocks for the further work towards a common data management for the emerging eLTER RI and also support the wider eLTER network.

eLTER is characterised by a distributed network of data providers linked mainly by means of metadata on sites and datasets. In order to comply to this situation, the eLTER Information System reflects central components for sharing and publishing data via the Central Data Node (CDN) and distributed components named as Partner Nodes (PN), as, for example, TERENO or OzCAR running their own data centres.

The eLTER Information System is composed of several components covering the main aspects of the data publication chain. The main components are:

- **Environmental Thesaurus [EnvThes]**¹³ controlled vocabulary (and related services), is used by the different components of the eLTER Information System. EnvThes provides the main semantic source for keywords and parameter names. It is used to annotate keywords to datasets during the metadating process. In the future, a central registration of reference lists should be possible.
- **DEIMS-SDR (Site and Dataset Registry) [DEIMS-SDR]**¹⁴, is a central service provided managing metadata on relevant information entities of the research infrastructure (e.g. network, research site, station, sensor, and person).
- **Data Repository or Data Node [DN]**¹⁵ (either local or central) provides services to manage, archive, and share data from long term observation and experimentation. The data can either be stored in a database, single files stores or already published applying time series or geo-spatial services (e.g. TERENO using OGC SOS)
- **Data Integration Portal [DIP]**¹⁶ harvests and integrates metadata from different provider nodes and acts as “one-stop-shop” for the discovery and access of metadata and data.

The eLTER Information System aims to adopt and implement standards wherever possible, being ISO19115/19139 and EML for MD, ISO19156 (O&M - Observation and Measurement)

¹³ see <http://vocabs.lter-europe.net/edg/tbl/EnvThes.editor>

¹⁴ see <https://deims.org/>

¹⁵ see <https://cdn.lter-europe.net/>

¹⁶ see <http://dip.lter-europe.net/>

for observation data, and in the long support (e.g. INSPIRE EF, Environmental and Monitoring Facility) data specification for site documentation.

The list of implemented and proposed components of the eLTER Information System was used in the ICT requirement analysis (i.e. by mapping the user stories and the derived epics to these components, see Chapter 3.2). Further development of the eLTER Information System and Data Architecture will be done by work package WP11 taking up the recommendations and requirements of the current report.

2.4.2 eLTER RI Proposed Topic Services Areas

In the frame of defining the requirements of the emerging eLTER RI, a number of eLTER RI Topic Service Areas (TSA) were proposed within the eLTER PPP proposal. They are designed to (a) ensure the support of scientific analysis, (b) integrate the different elements and functions of the RI and (c) provide focus for the outreach and interoperability with related RIs and research communities. The Topic Service Areas are closely connected with each other, to the operation of the eLTER national research infrastructures (NRIs), and to the Service Portal. They organise workflows for data capture and dissemination, training for both data management and reuse, and the design of services for users.

The proposed Topic Service Areas are currently:

- **Central Service Portal**, providing access to all RI capabilities including access to data sources from the eLTER (RI)
- **Data Quality Assurance for data**, developing standards, validation, and workflows for central data quality assurance for all RI capabilities
- **Modelling and Analysis Tools**, providing an analysis toolkit and community modelling platform
- **Technological Innovation and Development**, fostering partnerships for innovation, research and development of technologies outreach and interfaces, interoperable design development, fostering transdisciplinary research approaches, co-design, and synthesis
- **Design Interoperability and Synthesis**, focusing on research outreach and interfaces, interoperable design development, fostering transdisciplinary research approaches, co-design, and synthesis research

The Topic Service Areas are currently proposals and still under discussion. Nevertheless, we used the TSA in the analysis of the ICT requirement and mapped resulting “epics” to the TSA to provide a first linking to the activities of the emerging eLTER RI.

3 Methods

3.1 Data requirement collection

Based on the science cases and their scientific workflows, a collection of required data and variables was done in order to enable within-site and cross-site analysis. This was done together with RC leaders and contributors to the different science cases. The resulting variables were aligned across the different science cases and harmonised within WP10 by the RC leaders. The resulting list of data and variables are presented in Chapter 4.1 as well as in Annex 8.2.

Based on the resulting data requirements a survey was designed to collect the essential information and data availability needed for the next steps (e.g. to run the science cases, to perform further data calls). The eLTER PLUS Data Availability Survey was implemented at <https://survey.lter-europe.net> and it queried additional meta-information and data availability for the variables selected.

The survey was sent to the site managers using the LTER Europe mailing list. This mailing list covers all site contacts and contains approx. 420 recipients. In addition, a separate notification was sent to site and platform coordinators (SPCs) being beneficiaries of the eLTER PLUS project.

3.2 ICT Requirement collection

The implementation of the eLTER Information System (Watkins et al. 2015) is applying methods of *Agile* development¹⁷. These methods employ user stories to gather requirements and to start the development of services that users within the project and the emerging eLTER RI can use. These can cover a broad range of functions from a researcher and a data provider perspective. The development and testing of the components will modify the architecture specification to ensure it matches user needs. In addition, user stories will evolve in complexity and number over the life of the project to cover all areas of the architecture of the eLTER information system, while making sure that each cycle of development is relevant to the eLTER user community.

To map the wide range of needs of the communities, user-centric service design methods were used. For this step focus was given to two key communities, who are (a) the data provider (i.e. the main community providing data into the information system), and (b) the researcher (i.e. the user of the research data, but also potentially providing resulting data). These should cover the most topical needs in this project and so they were considered a good starting point. Further stakeholders and additional needs will be added later as this is a first iteration of describing requirements in this project.

In software development, a user story¹⁸ can be defined as an informal, natural language description of one or more features of the intended software system or data infrastructure,

¹⁷ see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Agile_software_development

¹⁸ see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/User_story

written from a user perspective addressing a system of interest. Within the current activities, user stories are used to capture the user perspective and map that into high-level use cases which we described as “epics” for the development.

3.2.1 User stories

In order to extract user stories from the community while taking to account the projects needs, as well as outreach to upcoming needs by the eLTER RI and potential eLTER RI users, a number of methods and working steps were conducted following a user-centric design approach. These were (a) targeted interviews with selected stakeholders to identify the scope and background of the eLTER Infrastructure, (b) workshops mapping user requirements based on personas derived from the interviews, and (c) analysis work on extracting the user stories.

Targeted interviews

In the first iteration targeted interviews were done with 11 researchers and 15 interviews with data providers (the latter with 26 participants) during October and November 2020. The first aimed to capture the researchers’ perspective as data users concerning both the context of eLTER Research Challenges and their scientific experience in general. The second aimed to represent the consolidated practices of the data providers and their background in using eLTER data management services. The interviews were semi-structured and covered a wide range of questions around data management processes. Some of the questions were technical while others concerned policies. It was difficult for any single respondent to answer all questions, as very few people have the skills to answer such a broad array of questions regarding data stewardship and management. An overview on the interview structure is given in Annex 8.3 and Annex 8.4. The difficulty in answering a wide range of specific questions during an interview was expected, and the interviewees were given the opportunity to provide additional details after consulting colleagues. Nevertheless, the main aim of the interviews was to get information about the future users of the eLTER service, their mindset, skills, workflows, processes, and priorities, to ensure that the services can facilitate and enable their work in the most relevant ways.

Requirements mapping

Based on the interview material, eight simple personas (i.e. fictional characters shaped to represent a user type), four researcher personas and four data provider personas were created. The aim of working with personas is to help the formulation of common needs, and thereby requirements, as well as facilitating a more abstract discussion about priorities without losing the common user focus. The personas represented different kinds of users with different profiles and needs which were derived from the interviews.

The personas were then processed in five online workshops during October -- December 2020. The first workshop about the researcher personas was held in conjunction with the eLTER Mercury meeting and was open for all participants at the meeting (about 45 participants in the workshop). The other four workshops were smaller and the invitations were targeted to

the interviewees as the workshop also had the function of validation (28 participants). As a workshop method, we chose empathy mapping (i.e., a collaborative visualization that represents knowledge about a user's behaviours and attitudes in a graphic map). The participants of the workshop used Mural boards to describe the actions, thoughts, and feelings of the different personas in a rich way.

This in turn created the material for writing user stories, 19 for the researchers and 21 for the data providers (Appendix 8.5). Relevant user stories from I-ADOPT were also included. Some of the user stories from the two groups were similar and this is also significant information when prioritising. In addition, the resulting user stories have been compared to the material collected for the eLTER project (see Oggioni et al., 2015) and checked for overlaps, gaps, and completeness.

3.2.2 Epics

Based on the analysis of the user stories collected, a number of “epics” were derived and described, as high level use cases. For each of the resulting epics, a basic description of the functionalities was provided and dependencies between the epics were defined. In addition, we analysed the epics in relation to:

- potential stakeholders of the emerging eLTER RI (see Chapter 2.2.1)
- components of the eLTER Information System (see Chapter 2.4.1)
- potential RI topic service areas (see Chapter 2.4.2)
- concepts of the ENVRI Reference Model (ENVRI-RM)¹⁹

The epics are input to the further architecture and information system design. In the runtime of the project, the user stories, as well as the resulting epics, will be reviewed and revised or extended if needed.

As a last step, ENVRI Reference model was used to discern whether there were requirements that had so far been left unnoticed.

¹⁹ see <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/EC/ENVRI+Reference+Model>

4 Results

4.1 Data needs from RC science cases

4.1.1 Biodiversity data

For WP 8 (whole system approach), ideally, biodiversity data should have at least been collected annually over at least 10 years with no change in method, season, and sampling location. In addition, several environmental data covering the same period and fulfilling the same criteria are needed to be used as explanatory variables in statistical analyses. As biodiversity covers very different taxa and these taxa occur in very different habitat types it is a challenge to a priori define specific taxa groups and/or environmental variables. In terms of feasibility, we therefore opted to approach sites with long-term biodiversity data (selection criteria: see above) which are also “data-rich” with regard to environmental variables (explorative approach). For WP 9 (continental scale approach), we applied the same criteria for biodiversity data as for WP 8, but mainly restricted the requirements for environmental parameters to those that are broadly available (e.g., from climate or land use models). This approach allows for both a higher coverage of a) taxonomic groups and b) a larger spatial scale at the expense of a lower resolution of the accompanied environmental driver data.

For the future, biodiversity research and monitoring would profit from a fully standardized and harmonized set of biodiversity standard observations. With this, many more sites could be used for various scientific analyses. The same applies to a suitable set of environmental standard observations that help interpreting changes in biodiversity.

4.1.2 Ecosystem data

Ecosystem monitoring data from priority sites defined in the project covering a time span of at least 10 years of plot- or catchment-based, medium (e.g. monthly) to high frequency (e.g. half hour) time series. To apply the eLTER’s whole-system approach in the analysis, a broad range of data are needed, covering biomass, climate, atmospheric deposition, soil-atmosphere gas exchange, air quality, soil climate, solid soil chemistry, soil water, runoff data, stream and standing water, groundwater, land use, and socio-economic data. Details regarding the variables, their units as well as the desired temporal resolution, are given in the data requirement table (see Annex 8.2). Table 2 provides a summarised view on the requirements indicating the number of variables per group considered.

Descriptive ecosystem data from priority sites and their observation units providing key characteristics on topography, vegetation type, soil physical characteristics, land cover and land use as well as habitat diversity. Details on variables and units are given in the data requirement table (see Annex 8.2).

The summary results are listed in Table 2 which provides the number of variables per group required by the science cases.

Table 2 Overview on variable groups for science cases in WP 8 and 9 and their respective tasks (8.1 to 9.4) indicating the number of variables

Science cases	8.1	8.2	8.3	8.4	9.1	9.2	9.3	9.4
TimeSeries								
Air quality		3				3		
Atmospheric deposition		10	10			10	10	
Biodiversity	15				15			
Biomass		8	3	2	1	8	3	2
Climate	2	3	10	2	4	3	10	2
Groundwater	1	1	3			3	1	
Land use		7	7	4	3	7	7	4
Runoff, streams and standing water	10		7		9	5	4	
Socio-economy	2			4				4
Soil climate	1	2	2		2	2	2	
Soil water		5	5			5	5	
Soil-atmosphere gas exchange		3	1			3	1	
Solid soil chemistry	6	6	6		6	6	6	
Descriptive site and plot data								
Habitat diversity	1					1		
Land cover	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Land use	1	1		2		1	3	2
Soil physics	2	8	9			8	9	
Topography		1				1		
Vegetation		1	1			1	1	
Remote Sensing	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Land cover	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Remote sensing								
	2							

In addition, the data requirement was used to define the data scope for the information management system of eLTER and was the source for the input into the overall data management plan developed by WP11.

4.1.3 Socio-ecological data

The question of data needs for the study of socio-ecological systems is a relatively new question, with few precedents which can serve as guidelines for what can be considered “essential” variables for understanding the dynamics of coupled social and ecological systems. Two iterations of expert consultations have taken place within eLTER over the past three years - the first within the framework of a previous H2020 eLTER collaborative project in 2018, where network socio-ecologists drafted the first list, presented in the LTSE Best Practices handbook (Orenstein et al. 2019). This list served as the basis for a second round of expert consultations conducted in the context of eLTER-PLUS and presented here (Table 2). This list was further cross-examined against emerging lists of essential socio-ecological data (e.g. Pacheco-Romero et al. 2020). Many of the essential variables are common across all themes and only a selection are required depending the specific research question asked.

In addition to being a new endeavour, essential data for understanding socio-ecological systems include both quantitative and qualitative variables. For the latter, there may not be an established protocol for collecting such data (e.g. “sense of place”). Indeed, objectives of the

SE Theme team within eLTER PLUS include adopting and testing protocol for the collection of such data.

Specific data needs for SE determined thus far include population (demographic) data, land use/land cover data, economic and resource-use data, environmental (abiotic) and ecological data, governance and property ownership regimes, ecosystem service profile, stakeholder engagement strategy, and data defining relational values between residents and their environment. We divide data into three availability categories:

- Data that is periodically collected and readily available from government or other established databases.
- Data that can be collected periodically using known and reliable protocol, but whose collection will likely be dependent on eLTER researchers and site/platform managers.
- Data for which there is no established protocol for collecting, but whose importance for understanding SE systems warrants the investment of eLTER-RI.

Five LTSER platforms will be engaged in first-round collection of the current data list. The list will be refined according to (1) the capacities of platforms to collect the data in an efficient and consistent manner (WP4.5) and (2) the assessed utility of the data for understanding SE systems (task 8.4). Some data, available in government and other databases, will be provided via an eLTER-sponsored online tools that will “cookie-cut” data according to spatially explicit boundaries (see Dick et al., 2020)²⁰. At this point, a complete list of variables is not defined but in WP4.2 the available data lodged with Eurostats, the statistical office of the European Union, is being interrogated and a list of potentially essential variables will be provided to the task leads of WP8 and WP9. Standard protocols for governance and property ownership regimes, ecosystem service profile, stakeholder engagement strategy, and data defining relational values between residents and their environment are being defined in tasks 8.4 and 9.4.

4.2 ICT needs from RC science cases

4.2.1 Non-functional requirements

eLTER collects and analyses long-term data sets to better understand patterns and processes in ecosystems and the interactions between ecosystems and socio-economic systems. eLTER supports and encourages the full and open sharing of ecological and socioeconomic data free of charge to advance research and education in the eLTER and for wider exploitation. eLTER documents and archives data for the benefit of present and future researchers as global environmental science becomes increasingly data driven. eLTER policies for data sharing and accessibility consider principles and policies developed by other

²⁰ see <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1xuTXJX6Vzx6wDyBVJAIurcBN1omIjMNR/edit>

global networks, including the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS)²¹ (GEOSS, 2009), the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2007), as well as recommendations by the European Commission on Open Data (EC, 2017)²² and INSPIRE (2007/2/EC)²³ that support sharing and open access to publicly funded research data.

eLTER encourages the public sharing of data and metadata, and promotes ad-hoc policies for sensitive data (e.g. rare species data). Data collected as a result of public funding to eLTER partners should be made available online with as few restrictions as possible, on a non-discriminatory basis. eLTER scientists should make every effort to release data in a timely fashion allowing for publication and citation of eLTER derived research and supporting data with attention to accurate and complete metadata.

eLTER should apply

- an open data license for scientific use
- a clear ownership and rights policy for all content (data, metadata, code, PIDs, etc.)

eLTER should comply to

- Open Data Pilots (H2020)
- comply to common standards for metadata (e.g. INSPIRE) and data
- comply to European regulations for data sharing (e.g. INSPIRE)
- support the FAIR data principles
- follow the GEO Data Sharing principles
- use of open standards for metadata and data wherever possible (e.g. OGC, W3C, ISO)

eLTER should take into account

- existing infrastructures in the eLTER context and reduce the amount of replication of information and data to a minimum possible
- evaluate the use of EOSC services to ensure European scale integration of services
- create a harmonized language in data management (e.g. training services for the community)

4.2.2 Functional requirements

Functional requirements are represented through epics. The epics described in this chapter are high-level use cases that are named according to the user goals that they represent for their primary stakeholders. The epics are written lists of actions and steps which describe the

²¹ see

https://www.earthobservations.org/documents/geo_vi/07_Implementation%20Guidelines%20for%20the%20GEOSS%20Data%20Sharing%20Principles%20Rev2.pdf

²² see http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oapilot-guide_en.pdf

²³ see <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32007L0002&from=EN>

essential interactions between a stakeholder and the eLTER information system to achieve a goal. The presented epics are based on the user stories described in Annex 8.5 (a selection of the relevant stories is presented for each epic) and they are identified according to the RI Topic Service Areas and the eLTER stakeholders. For each epic are provided a) a natural language description and b) putative maps to the ENVRI-RM and the eLTER information system components.

The epics include (currently) the following

- Epic Ingestion and upload of data objects
- Epic Publishing of data objects
 - Epic Creation of metadata on data objects
 - Epic Harvesting of metadata on data objects
- Epic Data curation
 - Epic Quality control and data manipulation
 - Epic Provenance tracking
- Epic Metadata discovery and visualisation of data objects
 - Epic Discovery of data objects
 - Epic Visualisation of data objects
- Develop workflows
 - Epic Creation eLTER data products
 - Epic Develop analytical workflows
- Epic Support and communication

The epic “Support and communication” can of course be regarded as an extension to all the other cases. The requirements regarding metadata concern use of semantic artefacts, tracking provenance, linking different versions of data and different outputs, as well as support for mapping metadata and creating citations. The epics span over the whole eLTER service portfolio and there will be further discussion on exactly which requirement will be feasible to implement in which service component. In this process, the FAIR principles and scientific reproducibility should be considered.

4.2.2.1 Epic Ingestion and upload of data objects

Description: A [user] wants to **deposit a data object** (e.g. dataset) using eLTER services. This includes the ingestion of data objects into the repository and assignment of PID during the ingestion process, so data objects are referenceable and citable. As a condition, descriptive and structural metadata following an agreed standard will be provided for the data object (see Epic Publishing of data).

Uploading and registering new data objects can either be done manually triggered by a [user] or by a [process], e.g. via automated data publishing pipelines from DataLab needs to be taken into account and included.

In addition, the access rights (e.g. in case of sensitive or GDPR relevant) for data objects need to be set.

This applies to the following data objects

- eLTER core datasets - defined as datasets collected in the frame of the eLTER Standard Observations (SO) and shared through the central data repository. The eLTER SOs will be defined in the runtime of the eLTER PLUS and eLTER PPP project.
- eLTER related datasets - defined as additional datasets generated by the eLTER sites and being shared through the central data repository.

The Ingestion and uploading of data objects include the following activities:

- uploading / registering of data objects
- validation and integrity checking of data objects
- confirmation and acceptance of data objects
- assignment of a PID to data objects
- documentation (including semantics, site, instruments)

In addition, the following actions need to be supported:

- Versioning of data objects, when updated data objects are uploaded using eLTER services.
- Selecting the appropriate licence to apply to data (e.g. free access, GDPR constraints, sharing with attribution to data owner)

Dependencies: Publishing of data objects, Data curation

Figure 6 Epic diagram Ingest and upload data objects

Stakeholders	Internal stakeholders, researchers and science stakeholders
Related eLTER IS components	Digital Asset Registry, CDN, EnvThes
Related Potential RI Service areas	Central Service Portal, Data Quality Assurance for data

ENVRI-RM Mapping:

- Data acquisition
 - Data collection
- Data processing
 - Workflow enactment
 - Processing control
- Data curation
 - Quality checking
- Community support
 - Authentication
 - Authorisation

Table 3 Related user stories for “Ingestion and upload of data objects”

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-D03	As a data provider, I want to upload my dataset, so that it can be stored in a secure way.	Digital Asset Registry, CDN
eLTER-US-R11	As a researcher I want to publish my research outputs, so that I can adhere to funder requirements.	Digital Asset Registry or EUDAT for DOIs; Data labs for workflows; DEIMS-SDR and Digital Asset Registry for metadata
eLTER-US-R04	As a researcher I want to do data conversions into recommended formats, so that I can use eLTER tools.	DataLabs, EnvThes, Semantics
eLTER-US-R02	As a researcher I need tools that support data collection and creation , so that my data is stored in a common format and I can use shared workflows.	DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DataLabs
eLTER-US-D04	As a data provider, I want to create metadata with minimal effort, so that I can publish rich metadata.	Digital Asset Registry, EnvThes, DEIMS-SDR
eLTER-US-D05	As a data provider, I want to import metadata , so that I don't have to type or copy-paste each value manually.	Digital Asset Registry, EnvThes, DEIMS-SDR, API
eLTER-US-D20	As a data provider, I want support in mapping metadata formats in a coherent way, so that the findability and metadata quality is optimal when importing metadata.	Digital Asset Registry, EnvThes, DEIMS-SDR, API
eLTER-US-R01	As a researcher I want to document the provenance of the data I have uploaded, so that my research is valid.	Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DataLabs
eLTER-US-D21	As a data provider, I want to publish different versions of my dataset from different stages of the life cycle (raw data, cleaned and validated data and a harmonised data product), so that different use cases are enabled and we get maximal gain from the data.	Digital Asset Registry
eLTER-US-R19	As a researcher I want to control the access to my sensitive research data, so that I can comply with GDPR and good scientific practice.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, CDN

4.2.2.2 Epic Publishing of data objects

4.2.2.2.1 Epic Creation of metadata on data objects

Description: A [user] wants to **provide metadata/information on data objects** (e.g. dataset, research output) and link it with a relevant data object using eLTER services. This online distribution link points either to existing data publication services or to a reference provided when directly uploading the data object into the proposed data infrastructure. This documentation includes links to the related information objects like sites, sensors, persons, or publications. In addition, a data provider would create metadata with minimal effort.

The Publication of data includes the following activities:

- creating descriptive, technical, and structural metadata
- linking all relevant objects and using semantic artefacts
- assigning a PID to the publication to enable citations
- using facilities for automatic compilation whenever possible

To ensure consistency and reusability:

- reference to specific metadata should be ensured
- metadata should point to the latest version of the data object described and should support versioning of the data
- metadata should be exhaustively compiled to allow the assessment of fitness for use

Prerequisites are:

- defined metadata model for data objects
- defined metadata model for sites
- defined metadata model for sensors
- defined link to provenance

Dependencies: Ingest and uploading of data, quality control and data manipulation, provenance tracking

Figure 7: Epic diagram Creation of metadata on data objects

Stakeholders	Internal stakeholders, researchers and science stakeholders
Related eLTER IS components	Digital Asset Registry, CDN, EnvThes, DEIMS-SDR
Related RI Topic Service areas	Central Service Portal

ENVRI-RM Mapping:

- Data access
 - Metadata harvesting
 - Resource registration
 - Access control
- Community support
 - Authentication
 - Authorisation
- Data curation
 - Quality checking
 - Preservation

Table 4 Related user stories for “Creation of metadata on data objects”

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-R05	As a researcher I want to publish a compiled dataset with provenance metadata , so that I can cite it.	Digital Asset Registry (once the RI is established and can mint DOIs), EUDAT, CDN, EnvThes
eLTER-US-R16	As a researcher I want to publish all my research outputs, so that I can get cited.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR (site reference), EUDAT
eLTER-US-D10	As a data provider, I want there to be a citation mechanism, so that I get credit for my work.	Digital Asset Registry
eLTER-US-R17	As a researcher I want to link my outputs , so that my research is reproducible.	Data labs, Digital Asset Registry
eLTER-US-D09	As a data provider, I want to have a rich data model, so that I can express the organization of my datasets in a clear way.	Digital Asset Registry
eLTER-US-D05	As a data provider, I want to import metadata , so that I don't have to type or copy-paste each value manually.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, EnvThes, api
eLTER-US-D04	As a data provider, I want to create metadata with minimal effort, so that I can publish rich metadata.	Digital Asset Registry, EnvThes, DEIMS-SDR

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-R09	As a researcher I want to use common semantic artefacts when I document my data, so that my data is interoperable.	EnvThes, Digital Asset Registry
eLTER-US-D14	As a data provider, I want my data and metadata to be validated , so that it can be reused.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, DataLabs
eLTER-US-R19	As a researcher I want to control the access to my sensitive research data, so that I can comply with GDPR and good scientific practice.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, CDN
eLTER-US-D21	As a data provider, I want to publish different versions of my dataset from different stages of the life cycle (raw data, cleaned and validated data and a harmonised data product), so that different use cases are enabled and we get maximal gain from the data.	Digital Asset Registry
eLTER-US-D19	As a data provider, I want to track the use of my data.	Digital Asset Registry

4.2.2.2.2 Epic Exposing and sharing of metadata on data objects

Description: A [user] wants to **provide metadata via API or service** (e.g. OGC CSW) to the central catalogue to be searchable via the central data catalogue. Metadata need to be provided in a standardised form to be ingested into the eLTER metadata store.

The Harvesting of metadata on data objects include the following activities:

- identification of metadata end point
- mapping of metadata models
- checking validity and consistency of metadata provided
- identification of duplicate metadata
- harvesting of metadata
- update and versioning of metadata

To ensure consistency and reusability:

- metadata need to be curated and updated frequently
- reference to specific metadata should be ensured
- metadata should point to the latest version of the data object described and should support versioning of the data
- metadata need to be compliant to the eLTER metadata schema

Prerequisites are:

- defined metadata model for data objects
- defined metadata model for sites
- defined metadata model for sensors
- defined link to provenance

Dependencies: Ingest and uploading of data, quality control and data manipulation, Provenance tracking

Figure 8: Epic diagram Exposing and sharing metadata on data objects

Stakeholders	Internal stakeholders (e.g. researcher and data provider), researchers and science stakeholders
Related eLTER IS components	Digital Asset Registry, CDN, EnvThes, DEIMS-SDR
Related RI Topic Service areas	Central Service Portal

ENVRI-RM Mapping:

- Data access
 - Metadata harvesting
 - Resource registration
 - Access control
- Community support
 - Authentication
 - Authorisation
- Data curation
 - Quality checking
 - Preservation

Table 5: Related user stories for “Exposing and sharing metadata on data objects”

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-D20	As a data provider, I want support in mapping metadata formats in a coherent way, so that the	

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
	findability and metadata quality is optimal when importing metadata.	
eLTER-US-D05	As a data provider, I want to import metadata, so that I don't have to type or copy-paste each value manually.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, EnvThes, api
eLTER-US-R16	As a researcher I want to publish all my research outputs, so that I can get cited.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR (site reference), EUDAT

4.2.2.3 Epic Data curation

4.2.2.3.1 Epic Quality control and data manipulation

Description: A [user] wants to **quality control and prepare data objects** before the ingestion and upload using eLTER services. This includes the validation of the content of the data object as well as the data structure according to defined requirements.

The Quality control and data manipulation includes the following activities:

- quality control
- assessment of data values
- flagging of outliers
- format control
- validation of structure
- conversions of structure

Prerequisites are:

- defined quality assessment and quality control procedures for different data types
- defined data structures for different data types

Dependencies: Ingestion and uploading of data

Figure 9: Epic diagram "Quality control and data manipulation"

Stakeholders	Data providers, researchers
Related eLTER IS components	DataLab / QC service, Digital Asset Registry, EnvThes
Potential RI Service areas	Central Service Portal, Quality Assurance for Data

ENVRI-RM Mapping:

- Data processing
 - Workflow enactment
 - Processing control
- Data curation
 - Quality checking
- Community support
 - Authentication
 - Authorisation

Table 6: Related user stories for “Quality control and data manipulation”

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-D16	As a data provider, I want to use common provided workflows to ensure quality control and checking on the data prior to data submission.	DataLab / QC service, EnvThes, Semantics
eLTER-US-D14	As a data provider, I want my data and metadata to be validated , so that it can be reused.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, DataLabs / QC service
eLTER-US-R04	As a researcher I want to do data conversions into recommended formats, so that I can use eLTER tools.	DataLabs, EnvThes, Semantics
eLTER-US-D13	As a data provider, I have to adhere to the INSPIRE directive, so that my publication is valid.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR
eLTER-US-R03	As a researcher I want to compare datasets , so that I can assess them.	Data labs for data analysis. DEIMS and Digital Asset Registry for metadata
eLTER-US-D20	As a data provider, I want support in mapping metadata formats in a coherent way, so that the findability and metadata quality is optimal when importing metadata.	Digital Asset Registry
eLTER-US-D01	As a data provider, I need support with creating a good data management plan, so that all data is compliant, interoperable and of good quality .	

4.2.2.3.2 Epic Provenance tracking

Description: A [user] wants to **track the data lifecycle and provenance** of a data object within, between, and outside the eLTER services in order to ensure re-usability of the data. This should include manipulation of data objects as well as the generation of new and derived datasets based on input data. Provenance information should be extracted from workflows (e.g. DataLab) as much as possible and should minimize human interaction and manual input. Provenance information should start with the data acquisition process (e.g. sensor, mapping)

The Provenance tracking includes the following activities:

- creating PIDs for related entities and linking these
- documenting data lifecycle events and linking these
- tracking use of entities

Prerequisites are:

- defined model for provenance recording
- defined linking to data object metadata

Dependencies: Publishing of data objects, ingestion and upload of data objects

Figure 10: Epic diagram "Provenance tracking"

Stakeholders	Internal stakeholders (e.g. researcher and data provider), researchers and science stakeholders
Related eLTER IS components	DataLab / QC service, Digital Asset Registry, EnvThes
Potential RI Service areas	Central Service Portal, Quality Assurance of data, Modelling and analysis tools

ENVRI-RM Mapping:

- Data acquisition
 - Data collection
- Data processing
 - Workflow enactment
- Data curation
- Community support
 - Authentication
 - Authorisation

Table 7: Related user stories for “Provenance tracking”

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-R05	As a researcher I want to publish a compiled dataset with provenance metadata , so that I can cite it.	Digital Asset Registry (once the RI is established and can mint DOIs), EUDAT, CDN, EnvThes
eLTER-US-R01	As a researcher I want to document the provenance of the data I have uploaded, so that my research is valid.	Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DataLabs
eLTER-US-R17	As a researcher I want to link my research outputs , so that my research is reproducible.	Data labs, Digital Asset Registry
eLTER-US-D19	As a data provider, I want to track the use of my data.	Digital Asset Registry (DOI and external services)
eLTER-US-D02	As a data provider, I want to have access to common protocols , so that datasets are harmonized as early as possible in the data lifecycle.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, EnvThes
eLTER-US-D04	As a data provider, I want to create metadata with minimal effort, so that I can publish rich metadata.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, EnvThes
eLTER-US-D18	As a data provider, I want to register my site and get a PID for it, so that I can link to it in my dataset description metadata.	DEIMS-SDR, PID, Semantics
eLTER-US-D17	As a data provider, I want to register my instruments and get a PID for them, so I can link to them in my documentation.	DEIMS-SDR, PID, Semantics
eLTER-US-D08	As a data provider, I want to link my dataset to sites and instruments , so that provenance and format are clear and unambiguous	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR
eLTER-US-D21	As a data provider, I want to publish different versions of my dataset from different stages of the life cycle (raw data, cleaned and validated data and a harmonised data product), so that different use cases are enabled and we get maximal gain from the data.	

4.2.2.4 Epic Metadata discovery and visualisation of data objects

4.2.2.4.1 Epic Discover data objects

Description: As [user] I want to **discover available data** objects from the eLTER network and RI and retrieve information (metadata) on the related data objects. This is true for the eLTER core datasets as well as for related eLTER datasets. Metadata should meet common standards and enable discovery based on selected facets, e.g. spatial scope, temporal scope, taxonomic scope, observed properties, and data policy. Metadata should also inform about the policy and terms of re-use (e.g. licenses) of the data.

The Discovery of data objects include the following activities:

- search based on specific facets

- discover and view selected metadata
- access or transparent requesting, and download of data objects

Dependencies: Ingest and uploading of data objects, quality control and data manipulation, provenance tracking, publishing of data objects

Figure 11: Epic diagram "Discover data objects"

Stakeholders	Internal stakeholders (e.g. researcher and data provider), researchers and science stakeholders, government and policy decision makers, peers in environmental research and observation, research infrastructures
Related eLTER IS components	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, EnvThes, EcoSense
Related Potential RI Service areas	Central Service Portal

ENVRI-RM Mapping:

- Data access
 - Metadata harvesting
 - Access control
- Community support
 - Authentication
 - Authorisation

Table 8: Related user stories for "Discover data objects"

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-R20	As a researcher I want to search/discover datasets provided by the eLTER RI and eLTER network to be used in research.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, EcoSense
eLTER-US-R03	As a researcher I want to compare datasets , so that I can assess them.	Data labs for data analysis. DEIMS and Digital Asset Registry for metadata
eLTER-US-R08	As a researcher I want to contact the data provider , so that I can validate the suitability of the dataset for my research.	DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset Registry

4.2.2.4.2 Epic Visualise data objects

Description: As [user] I want to **preview and visualise data** objects shared via the central data repository. This includes geo-spatial data as well as time series available online in a defined format. A preview of the data prior to download and access is recommended for a generic user. This needs to include the eLTER core data and data products as well as related data from the eLTER network.

The Visualisation of data objects include the following activities:

- discovery of data object
- selection of temporal extent for time series data
- visualisation of data object based on data type
- access and download of data objects

Dependencies: Ingest and data uploading of data objects, publishing of data objects, discovery of data objects

Figure 12: Epic diagram "Visualise data objects"

Stakeholders	Internal stakeholders (e.g. researcher and data provider), researchers and science stakeholders
Related eLTER IS components	Digital Asset Registry, CDN, EcoSense
Related Potential RI Service areas	Central Service Portal

ENVRI-RM Mapping:

- Data processing
 - Workflow enactment
 - Processing control
- Data access
- Community support
 - Authentication
 - Authorisation

Table 9: Related user stories for "Visualise data objects"

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-U01	As a USER, I want to visualise data (spatial and time series) of interest for visual inspection of the data.	Digital Asset Registry, EcoSense, DataLab

4.2.2.5 Develop workflows

4.2.2.5.1 Epic Create eLTER data product

Description: A [research infrastructure] wants to **produce a harmonised data product** using eLTER services and publish and share the resulting data object via eLTER services. Existing data objects are subject to a defined workflow to create and validate the data product. This can either be done in a single process or can be initiated based on a defined interval depending on the input data. In addition, versioning of the data product needs to be supported. Metadata should be created automatically based on the underlying workflows. The workflows need to be published in addition to the resulting data object.

The Creation of eLTER Data Products include the following activities:

- developing common workflows
- sharing and documenting the common workflows
- ingestion of documented data (including PID)
- application of the common workflow
- validation and QC of resulting data product
- automatic generation of metadata
- publishing of data product
- versioning of data product

The following actions need to be supported:

- calculate and assure the legal interoperability of data objects used to build the data product (i.e. the legal use condition of each data set is assessed and the combination of them is assured)

The activities need to include also automated processes on how to publish the resulting data products from DataLab workflows.

Dependencies: Ingest and uploading of data objects, quality control and data manipulation, provenance tracking, publishing of data objects

Figure 13: Epic diagram "Create eLTER data product"

Stakeholders	Internal stakeholders (e.g. researcher and data provider), researchers and science stakeholders, government and policy decision makers, peers in environmental research and observation, research infrastructures
Related eLTER IS components	DataLab, Digital Asset Registry, CDN, EnvThes
Related Potential RI Service areas	Central Service Portal, Quality Assurance for Data, Modelling and Analysis Tools

ENVRI-RM Mapping:

- Data acquisition
 - Data collection
 - Measurement control
- Data access
 - Metadata harvesting
- Data processing
 - Workflow enactment
 - Processing control
- Data curation
 - Quality checking

- Resource registration
- Access control
- Preservation
- Community support
 - Authentication
 - Authorisation

Table 10: Related user stories for “Create eLTER data product”

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-D21	As a data provider, I want to publish different versions of my dataset from different stages of the life cycle (raw data, cleaned and validated data and a harmonised data product), so that different use cases are enabled and we get maximal gain from the data.	Digital Asset Registry, EnvThes, Semantics, DataLab
eLTER-US-D16	As a data provider, I want to use common provided workflows to ensure quality control and checking on the data prior to data submission.	DataLab

4.2.2.5.2 Epic Develop analytical workflows

Description: A [user] wants to develop analytical workflows using a wide range of data and RI services to generate new knowledge. These data and RI services may extend beyond eLTER digital assets but must be accessible through (or compatible with) the eLTER analytical workflow services. The resulting workflows are shared and can be reused by other [researchers]. The resulting data from the analytical workflow may or may not be stored. The resulting workflows form a key link to other RIs to tackle cross-disciplinary questions.

The Research workflows include the following activities:

- documentation and discovery of existing workflows / sharing of analytical workflows
- identifying what type of metadata are needed to describe the workflows

Prerequisites are:

- metadata model to document resulting analytical workflows
- repository to share the code of the resulting analytical workflow

Dependencies: Ingest and uploading of data objects, quality control and data manipulation, provenance tracking, publishing of data objects, metadata discovery and access

Figure 14: Epic diagram “Develop analytical workflows”

Stakeholders	Internal stakeholders (e.g. researchers), researchers and science stakeholders, peers in environmental research and observation, related research infrastructures
Related eLTER IS components	Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DataLab
Related Potential RI Service areas	Central Service Portal, Modelling and Analysis Tools

ENVRI-RM Mapping:

- Data acquisition
 - Data collection
 - Measurement control
- Data processing
 - Workflow enactment
 - Processing control
- Community support
 - Authentication
 - Authorisation
- Data access
 - Metadata harvesting
 - Resource registration
 - Access control
- Data curation
 - Quality checking

Table 11: Related user stories for “Develop analytical workflows”

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-D15	As a data provider, I want to take part in developing workflows and services , so that they can be developed continuously.	DataLabs
eLTER-US-R14	As a researcher I want to manage my workflows and share them, so that I get more citations	DataLabs, GitHub
eLTER-US-R07	As a researcher I want to manage different versions of my code , so that I can track errors.	DataLabs, GitHub
eLTER-US-R11	As a researcher I want to publish my research outputs , so that I can adhere to funder requirements.	Digital Asset Registry or EUDAT for DOIs; Data labs for workflows; DEIMS-SDR and Digital Asset Registry for metadata

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-R16	As a researcher I want to publish all my research outputs , so that I can get cited .	Digital Asset Registry or EUDAT for DOIs; Data labs for workflows; DEIMS-SDR and Digital Asset Registry for metadata
eLTER-US-R06	As a researcher I want to manage different versions of my data , so that I can track errors.	Digital Asset registry, DataLabs
eLTER-US-D02	As a data provider, I want to have access to common protocols , so that datasets are harmonized as early as possible in the data lifecycle.	Digital Asset registry, EnvThes, DataLabs
eLTER-US-R15	As a researcher I want documentation to be automatic when possible, so that the metadata and links are standardized	DataLabs, Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DEIMS, DIP
eLTER-US-D04	As a data provider, I want to create metadata with minimal effort, so that I can publish rich metadata.	Digital Asset Registry, EnvThes, DEIMS-SDR
eLTER-US-D05	As a data provider, I want to import metadata , so that I don't have to type or copy-paste each value manually.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, EnvThes, api
eLTER-US-D06	As a data provider, I want to export metadata , so that I don't have to type or copy-paste each value manually.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, api
eLTER-US-R02	As a researcher I need tools that support data collection and creation, so that my data is stored in a common format and I can use shared workflows.	Digital Asset registry, Data labs, DEIMS-SDR, CDN
eLTER-US-R01	As a researcher I want to document the provenance of the data I have uploaded, so that my research is valid.	Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DataLabs
eLTER-US-R05	As a researcher I want to publish a compiled dataset with provenance metadata, so that I can cite it.	Digital Asset registry, EnvThes, DataLabs, EUDAT, CDN
eLTER-US-R04	As a researcher I want to do data conversions into recommended formats, so that I can use eLTER tools.	DataLabs, EnvThes
eLTER-US-D14	As a data provider, I want my data and metadata to be validated , so that it can be reused.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, DataLabs
eLTER-US-R08	As a researcher I want to contact the data provider , so that I can validate the suitability of the dataset for my research.	DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset Registry
eLTER-US-R10	As a researcher I want to contact the service provider , to apply for more resources.	DataLabs

4.2.2.6 Epic Support and communication

Description: A [user] needs to **interact with the services** and to communicate with data providers. This includes the relevant documentation of the services and tools provided as well as training and capacity building.

The Support and communication includes the following activities:

- training
- feedback

- service requests
- rights & access management by data owner (Data Management Plan)
- contact with data provider

Dependencies: -

Figure 15: Epic diagram “Support and communication”

Stakeholders	Internal stakeholders (e.g. researchers), researchers and science stakeholders, peers in environmental research and observation
Related eLTER IS components	Training and capacity building
Related Potential RI Service areas	Central Service Portal

ENVRI-RM Mapping: -

Table 12: Related user stories for “Support and communication”

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-D01	As a data provider, I need support with creating a good data management plan , so that all data is compliant, interoperable and of good quality.	central eLTER Info System training resources
eLTER-US-R18	As a researcher I want to control how my data is stored , so that I can influence the retention time.	central eLTER Info System training resources
eLTER-US-R12	As a researcher I want training , so that I can use the tools efficiently.	central eLTER Info System training resources
eLTER-US-R13	As a researcher I need support with optimizing my code, so that I can be as fast as the next group.	central eLTER Info System contact system

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-D15	As a data provider, I want to take part in developing workflows and services , so that they can be developed continuously.	central eLTER Info System training resources
eLTER-US-R10	As a researcher I want to contact the service provider , to apply for more resources.	central eLTER Info System contact system
eLTER-US-R19	As a researcher I want to control the access to my sensitive research data , so that I can comply with GDPR and good scientific practice .	central eLTER Info System training resources
eLTER-US-D11	As a data provider, I want to restrict access to the dataset , so that I can publish data that cannot be made openly available.	central eLTER Info System training resources
eLTER-US-R08	As a researcher I want to contact the data provider, so that I can validate the suitability of the dataset for my research.	central eLTER Info System contact system

4.2.2.7 Metadata requirements

Metadata are key to discovery and reuse of datasets from various sources. This is already addressed by the eLTER community profile (see, for example, Poursanidis et al., 2017) implemented by DEIMS-SDR to document datasets and data products. In addition, the eLTER Data Specification²⁴ also takes into account a number of metadata requirements (e.g. information on stations, methods, observation events, samples, or license) in order to ensure the re-usability of the data.

In the interviews, one of the questions addressed the aspect of data discovery asking for the most relevant aspects to search for data. Beside the variables covered, especially the spatial and temporal extent, the completeness and quality of information, the length of the time series, and information on the data provider and data use policies were mentioned.

In addition, based on the user stories, a number of general requirements can be derived, which are in line with the epics mentioned above. The following list is not exclusive, but addresses aspects mentioned during the interview and formulation of the user stories:

- Provenance information
- Quality information
- Method information (e.g. on sensors deployed, models applied)
- Contact information
- Data usage and license information

Also, compliance and mapping into relevant metadata standards (e.g. INSPIRE metadata specification) was mentioned.

²⁴ See https://www.lter-europe.net/projects/PLUS/eLTER_TechDoc_TemplateSpecification.pdf

Table 13: Related user stories to address common metadata requirements

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-R11	As a researcher I want to publish my research outputs, so that I can adhere to funder requirements.	Digital Asset Registry or EUDAT for DOIs; Data labs for workflows; DEIMS-SDR and Digital Asset Registry for metadata
eLTER-US-R16	As a researcher I want to publish all my outputs, so that I can get cited .	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR (site reference), EUDAT
eLTER-US-D04	As a data provider, I want to create metadata with minimal effort , so that I can publish rich metadata.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, EnvThes
eLTER-US-R15	As a researcher I want documentation to be automatic where possible, so that the metadata and links are standardized	DataLabs, Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DEIMS, DIP
eLTER-US-R05	As a researcher I want to publish a compiled dataset with provenance metadata , so that I can cite it.	Digital Asset Registry (once the RI is established and can mint DOIs), EUDAT, CDN, EnvThes
eLTER-US-R01	As a researcher I want to document the provenance of the data I have uploaded, so that my research is valid and reusable.	Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DataLabs
eLTER-US-R17	As a researcher I want to link my outputs, so that my research is reproducible .	Data labs, Digital Asset Registry
eLTER-US-R03	As a researcher I want to compare datasets , so that I can assess them.	Data labs for data analysis. DEIMS and Digital Asset Registry for metadata
eLTER-US-R06	As a researcher I want to manage different versions of my data, so that I can track errors.	Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DataLabs
eLTER-US-R08	As a researcher I want to contact the data provider , so that I can validate the suitability of the dataset for my research.	DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset registry
eLTER-US-R19	As a researcher I want to control the access to my sensitive research data , so that I can comply with GDPR and good scientific practice.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, CDN
eLTER-US-D02	As a data provider, I want to have access to common protocols , so that datasets are harmonized as early as possible in the data lifecycle.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, EnvThes
eLTER-US-D07	As a data provider, I want to choose which semantic artefacts I use, so that I can use relevant subject headings and terminology	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, EnvThes
eLTER-US-D12	As a data provider, I need metadata in several languages , so that my national government and public can find the data.	Digital Asset Registry, EnvThes/Semantics

eLTER US code	User Story	Related components
eLTER-US-D08	As a data provider, I want to link my dataset to sites and instruments , so that provenance and format are clear and unambiguous	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR
eLTER-US-D09	As a data provider, I want to have a rich data model, so that I can express the organization of my datasets in a clear way.	Digital Asset Registry
eLTER-US-D05	As a data provider, I want to import metadata , so that I don't have to type or copy-paste each value manually.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, EnvThes, api
eLTER-US-D13	As a data provider, I have to adhere to the INSPIRE directive, so that my publication is valid.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR
eLTER-US-D14	As a data provider, I want my data and metadata to be validated , so that it can be reused.	Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, DataLabs
eLTER-US-D20	As a data provider, I want support in mapping metadata formats in a coherent way, so that the findability and metadata quality is optimal when importing metadata.	

5 Mapping of User story to ENVRI-RM

By comparing requirements in the epics to ENVRI Reference model (see also Annex 8.6), it can be noticed that in data acquisition, functionality parameter visualization, processing, and process control issues do not have corresponding eLTER requirements. This can be considered as a topic for further eLTER architecture work. Should eLTER RI architecture include control of onsite equipment and instruments or not?

ENVRI Reference model Data Curation functionality block is quite well covered by the presented use cases. On site and between sites, data management issues will have to be included in eLTER RI technical requirements.

Data Publishing functionality contains features used to take and process internally stored data products and “making them publicly available”. This process may contain steps like data compression, metadata harvesting, and more. eLTER architecture must take care that all necessary steps from keeping data in an internal repository to data publishing are tended to. In addition, necessary resource repositories must be defined.

Although at first sight these recommendations seem not to match clearly with the ENVRI model Data processing functions, epic Creation of the eLTER data products is, in fact, a very close match. In addition to workflow support, eLTER RI architecture should define what kind of standard data processing tools are needed.

The last case, Data Use functionalities, discusses the end user perspective. The eLTER RI architecture should define how end users will use eLTER infrastructure services. Event notification functionality is a feature that could be useful. It should therefore be taken into account within eLTER RI architecture.

6 Next steps

eLTER PLUS is working and supporting the establishment of the emerging eLTER RI by showcasing and developing core elements of the information architecture and prototyping basic workflows. The development needs to be guided by a co-design approach taking into account (a) the user perspective (reflected by the science cases), (b) the data perspective (reflected by the eLTER site capabilities), and (c) the technological perspective (reflected by the central IT capabilities). In the coming months, WP10, dealing with the definition of core data and ICT needs and pilot data workflows, will focus on the selection of workflows to enable harmonised and standardised eLTER data products in cooperation with the science cases within the project.

The development of workflows for creating the first eLTER Data Products relevant for cross science case analysis will be a good showcase to align the infrastructure needs and developments and combine it with current or future user needs. This will cover and address most of the epics outlined in chapter 4.2, ranging from the Development of workflows (see 4.2.2.5), the Curation of data (see 4.2.2.3), as well as the Ingestion and storage of data (see 4.2.2.1) and the Documentation of the resulting datasets (see 4.2.2.2).

Through this, a proof of concept and testing of the underlying working steps in terms of semantic enrichment, provenance tracking and access policies can easily be done. This process also fits into the development of the Topic Service Areas.

The development and implementation of the service components of the eLTER Information System is done by WP11 ICT Service piloting and dissemination of data products, which will require tight interaction with WP4, WP8, WP9 and WP10.

6.1 Develop eLTER data products

In eLTER PLUS WP8 and WP9, site and platform data is going to be transformed into harmonized data sets applicable for cross-site and cross platform analyses and modelling. This work will include various analysis workflows such as formatting, unit harmonization, aggregation, gap filling, and more. The resulting data products will be shared with the wider scientific communities. Until now, data are collected from the eLTER sites fitting the data needs mentioned above (see chapter 4.1). While processing the data has not yet begun, first discussions on the development of common eLTER data products have taken place, which resulted in a number of general recommendations as follows:

- Data products must include proper metadata, as well as provision of related information (e.g. code, model, licenses). Tracking the provenance will be of particular importance in order to ensure the re-usability of the data.
- When workflows for the creation of model input is the aim, we recommend restricting to a few model types and a small number of frequently used models (as a start, in order to take feasible steps; eLTER PLUS – WP8/WP9 will introduce their models, and we may add additional ones)

- Procedures which produce gapless time series data and one-off measurements for a defined location (plot, catchment, site) are important
- Transparency regarding the data sources, processing steps (the raw data must always be available as a supplement to the product) and the licences applied to allow the reuse
- Data products for modellers should complement existing products (focus on obvious data gaps, as we have already done in eLTER H2020, for example, with historic N and S modelled and measured deposition time series using EMEP data together with measurements)
- The products should be available in a standard format, or as a machine-readable service (e.g. OGC SOS)

Such data products will reflect Level 3 data which will be developed during the course of the eLTER PLUS project. Special emphasis will be given to this subject in WP8, 9, 10 and WP3, defining the eLTER Standard Observations (SO). Tasks 10.2 and 10.3 will focus particularly on these objectives together with the science cases.

6.2 Make eLTER FAIR

The design and implementation of the eLTER Information System, especially with focus on the provided data services and workflows, need to take into account the FAIR principles as common guidelines. Technical solutions can either be developed or implemented for the existing components or otherwise implemented by adopting existing services provided (e.g. by other RIs or EOSC).

Persistent Identification (PID) for the different entities addressed in the data life cycle should be used where possible. This addresses the following aspects: (a) enable PIDs for datasets (including dynamic datasets), (b) enable PIDs for instruments, (c) enable PIDs for sites and platforms, (d) enable PIDs for samples, (e) use of ORCID IDs for researchers, (f) use Funder and Project Identifiers when required and available, (g) use Semantic artefacts for creating metadata, and (h) enable further PIDs for workflows and codes would support a FAIR Ecosystem.

Metadata should be exposed as FAIR as possible. In addition, eLTER services should also provide signposting to existing metadata and provide metadata in a machine actionable form if possible. Inter-alia, common metadata schemas (e.g. DCAT 2) should be evaluated in addition to ISO19115/19139 to ensure cross-community metadata exchange. Metadata should be as machine readable as possible and semantic artefacts should be well supported.

Data and metadata provenance and ownership should be managed in such ways that the eLTER infrastructure can be considered a trustworthy service provider. Clear policies have to be implemented and must have an owner that is possible to reach and someone that is responsible for the accuracy and curation of the metadata. GDPR and other legislation also requires that there be a legally responsible owner of the data. In practice, this means that there should be an organisational fall back with sufficient rights in case

the content owner is an individual or a group of individuals. There should be contracts in place between these individuals and the organization that ensure rights and ownership of the content in different situations. It can also be noted that in practice a large number of rights holders for the same content might make reuse or transactions difficult, as separate contracts are needed with everyone, and that the more open and permissive a licence is, the easier the management of the content, including metadata, will be. Therefore, eLTER should support rights management during the whole data life cycle with good and strong policy recommendations and practices (i.e. templates, policies, and licences). Legal interoperability is an important prerequisite for interoperability.

Use rights (licence) should be separated from **access rights** in the metadata and contractually. These should both be machine readable, as should all restrictions and preferably also the related restriction reason.

Table 14: Mapping of epics to proposed topic service areas with regard to FAIR principles

	Central Service Portal	Data Quality Assurance for data	Modelling and Analysis Tools	Technological Innovation and Development	Design Interoperability and Synthesis
Epic: Ingestion and upload of data objects	FAIR enabling	supporting		supporting	supporting
Epic: Publishing of data objects	FAIR enabling	supporting		supporting	supporting
Epic: Data curation	FAIR enabling	FAIR enabling	supporting	supporting	supporting
Epic: Metadata discovery and visualisation of data objects	FAIR enabling	supporting	supporting	supporting	FAIR enabling
Epic: Creation eLTER data products	FAIR enabling	FAIR enabling	FAIR enabling	supporting	FAIR enabling
Epic: Develop analytical workflows	supporting	supporting	supporting		
Epic: Support & communication	supporting				

Table 14 summarises the mapping of the FAIR principles to the suggested eLTER RI Service Topic Areas and the Epics. It provides an overview on the relevance of the FAIR principles with regard to the proposed topic service areas of the emerging eLTER RI. The cells marked in green colour highlights the scope of the epic with regard to the planned topic service areas. In this context, “FAIR enabling” means that the FAIR data principles should be considered as be requirements in the services, whereas “Supporting” means that taking the FAIR principles into account through planning for metadata, identifiers, provenance tracking and common semantic artefacts the FAIR Ecosystem is strengthened and scientific reproducibility enhanced.

6.3 Develop infrastructure components

Based on epics' content, a number of new requirements were collected which had not been addressed so far. In particular, dealing with data curation and access will be important issues for the coming developments. In order to proceed with the implementation of the eLTER Information System, several components addressed in the user requirements will be evaluated in the ongoing development process:

- **Metadata and data sharing** - Digital Asset Registry [DAR], is a central catalogue developed and provided to document and publish metadata on eLTER Core Datasets and Data products. This also includes the extension of the current functionalities of the eLTER Central Data Node to cover a wider range of data types.
- **Visualisation** - EcoSense, is a newly developed component for visualisation of time-series and spatial data published through the eLTER Information System as services. EcoSense also will allow linking to spatial data services, e.g. for derived EO data.
- **Analytical workflows** - DataLab, is an analytical platform developed and provided within the eLTER PLUS project (as defined in the DoA) in order to enable analysis of data shared in the eLTER Information and combined with third party and local data. The DataLabs will also be used to develop common workflows for data manipulation and analysis.
- **Code repository** - e.g. eLTER GitLab for providing a common repository to publish and share code and workflows with the scientific community.
- **Rights and access management**, a centralised provisioning and user identity management service with functionalities like identity consolidation, group management, and rights entitlement to enable integrated workflows across services for groups and organisations. This could maybe be solved with common European tools (i.e. ESOC AAI), or should at least be interoperable with these.

In addition, there is a need for additional services for the eLTER Information System

- the extension of semantic services following the recommendations of the RDA i-Adopt working group
- integration of a PID service to identify the objects in the data life cycle
- integration of a provenance service to track links within the data life cycle

This will be taken up by WP11 in further defining their implementation strategy for the services requested. User requirements will be an important input in this process and checked iteratively during the implementation process in a systematic manner.

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7 References

- Berners Lee, T. (2006), Linked Data - Design Issues. Online <http://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html> [Last Accessed 12.6.2019 14:30]
- Collins, P., Patel, V., Joestl, S. et al. (2011). Grand challenges in global mental health. *Nature* 475, 27–30. <https://doi.org/10.1038/475027a>
- Haberl, H., V. Winiwarter, K. Andersson, R. U. Ayres, C. Boone, A. Castillo, G. Cunfer, M. Fischer-Kowalski, W. R. Freudenburg, E. Furman, R. Kaufmann, F. Krausmann, E. Langthaler, H. Lotze-Campen, M. Mirtl, C. L. Redman, A. Reenberg, A. Wardell, B. Warr, and H. Zechmeister (2006). From LTER to LTSER: conceptualizing the socioeconomic dimension of long-term socioecological research. *Ecology and Society* 11(2): 13. [online] URL: <http://www.ecologyandsociety.org/vol11/iss2/art13/>
- Krauze, K., Dick, J., Holzer, J., Włodarczyk-Marciniak, R., Pugnetti, A., Nikolaidis, N., Peterseil, J. (2018). D 5.3: Best practices in stakeholder engagement. eLTER (GA-Nr. 654359). Project deliverable [<https://www.lter-europe.net/document-archive/elter-h2020-project-files/d05-3-best-practices-in-stakeholder-engagement/view>]
- Kunkel, R., Peterseil, J., Oggioni, A., Wohner, C., Watkins, J., Minic, V., Sorg, J. (2019) D3.2 Governance and data policy for sharing and publishing of data. Project report of the eLTER (H2020) project (GA.Nr. 654359). 38pp.
- Kunkel, R., Sorg, J. (2016). Time Series Management System for sensor observation data (TSM). Core system technical description. Technical Document Research Centre Jülich. 80pp.
- Mollenhauer, H., Kasner, M., Haase, P., Peterseil, J., Wohner, C., Frenzel, M., Mirtl, M., Schima, R., Bumberger, J., Zacharias, S. (2018). Long-term environmental monitoring infrastructures in Europe: observations, measurements, scales, and socio-ecological representativeness. *Science of The Total Environment*, Volume 624, Pages 968-978, ISSN 0048-9697, [<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.12.095>].
- Oggioni, A., Wohner, C., Watkins, J., Ciar, D., Schentz, H., Lanucara, S., Minic, V., Skribic, S., Bodroski, Z., Kunkel, R., Sorg, J., Kliment, T., Sanchez, F., Magagna, B., Peterseil, J. (2015). D3.1 eLTER State of the art and requirements. eLTER (GA-Nr. 654359). Project deliverable [<https://www.lter-europe.net/document-archive/elter-h2020-project-files/d3-1-data-integration>].
- Open Knowledge Foundation (2019) Open Data Handbook. Online <http://opendatahandbook.org/guide/en/> [Last Accessed 12.6.2019 14:45]
- Orenstein, D.E., Adamescu, M.C., Angelstam, P., Dick, J., Diaz-Delgado, R., Holzer, J.M., Krauze, K., Santos-Reis, M., Sijtsma, F. (2019). Long-Term Socio-Ecological Research Platforms: A Best Practices Guidebook. Project deliverable
- Pacheco-Romero, M., Alcaraz-Segura, D., Vallejos, M., & Cabello, J. (n.d.). An expert-based reference list of variables for characterizing and monitoring social-ecological systems. *Ecology and Society*, 25(3). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-11676-250301>
- Pilotto, F., Kühn, I., Adrian, R. et al. (2020). Meta-analysis of multidecadal biodiversity trends in Europe. *Nat Commun* 11, 3486. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-17171-y>
- Poursanidis, D., Peterseil, J., Wohner, C., Chrysolakis, N., Wetzel, F., Alonso, J., Castro, P., Beierkuhnlein, C., Bernd, A., Zabla, A., Maso, J., Domingo, C., Vetaas, O., Bargmann, T., Bosch, S. (2017) D5.2 Metadata for pre-existing datasets. *Ecopotential* (GA.Nr. 641762). Project deliverable [<http://ecopotential-project.eu/images/ecopotential/documents/D5.2.pdf>]

Watkins, J., Ciar, D., Wohner, C., Peterseil, J., Schentz, H., Oggioni, A., Lanucara, S., Minic, V., Skribic, S., Bodroski, Z., Kunkel, R., Sorg, J. (2015). D8.1 eLTER Information Architecture Report. eLTER (GA-Nr. 654359). Project deliverable [<https://www.lter-europe.net/document-archive/elter-h2020-project-files/d8-1-it-design>].

Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L.B., Bourne, Ph.E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A.J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, Ch.T., Finkers, R., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gray, A. J.G., Groth, P., Goble, K., Grethe, J. S., Heringa, J., 't Hoen, P. A.C, Hooft, R., Kuhn, T., Kok, R., Kok, J., Lusher, S. J., Martone, M. E., Mons, A., Packer, A. L., Persson, B., Rocca-Serra, Ph., Roos, M., van Schaik, R., Sansone, S.-A., Schultes, E., Sengstag, Th., Slater, T., Strawn, G., Swertz, M. A., Thompson, M., van der Lei, J., van Mulligen, E., Velterop, J., Waagmeester, A., Wittenburg, P., Wolstencroft, K., Zhao, J., Mons, B. (2016): The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* 3 [2016/03/15/online; <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>]

Wohner, C., Peterseil, J., Poursanidis, D., Klimont, T., Wilson, M., Mirtl, M. & Chrysoulakis, N. (2019) DEIMS-SDR – A web portal to document research sites and their associated data. *Ecological Informatics*, 51:15-24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2019.01.005>.

8 Annexes

8.1 Description of eLTER PLUS Science Cases

Task 8.1 – High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change

Task aims to determine and prioritise the stressors affecting long-term changes in biodiversity and identify indicators for characterising short-term variability and long-term trends in biodiversity. We make use of a relevant subset of data-rich eLTER Sites to quantify long-term trends and short-term variability in biodiversity, and relate both to changes in abiotic variables and socio-ecological parameters in order to a) explain trends and patterns in biodiversity, b) determine and rank the stressors affecting long-term changes in biodiversity trends, and explain short-term variability in response to pulse disturbance across major European ecosystems and c) identify appropriate indicators of ecosystem response. We will use state-of-the-art modelling techniques (e.g. biomod2, INLA-system-dynamic modelling) that are capable of dealing with short-term as well as long-term temporal trends in a spatially non-independent context, and consider gaps in datasets. This approach allows us to evaluate the strength and added value of these unique eLTER datasets to (i) improve our understanding of how and why these ecosystems are changing, (ii) determine implications for ecosystem resilience and (iii) develop mitigation/adaptation measures.

Task 8.2 – Plot scale ecosystem process understanding

Task aims to increase process understanding of the impact of climate change and extreme weather events on C & N cycling and feedbacks in a broad range of ecosystems. Data on C and nutrient stocks & fluxes, climate, N deposition & management from eLTER Sites will be analysed; gap-filled using available models, such as EMEP for N deposition; and time series analyses will be applied. Extreme weather events (e.g. drought) will be characterised. Normalisation approaches, such as empirical probability density functions, will be used for cross-site comparisons. This will facilitate (i) identification of critical environmental thresholds and tipping points in C and N turnover and fluxes across the eLTER spectrum of ecosystems, climate zones and socio-ecological context and (ii) improvement of our understanding of the impact of extreme weather events and climate change on ecosystem processes. eLTER Site data will be complemented with remote sensing data from WP4, in order to evaluate the added value and the suitability of eLTER long-term data series to provide signals reflecting the influence of climate change on ecosystem processes.

Task 8.3 – Water use efficiency (WUE) of ecosystems and resilience to drought

Task aims to improve knowledge of the impact of drought events on ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) and resilience, and to understand relationships between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience. Data from 10 well-instrumented sites that cross climatic, geological and socio-ecological regions will be used to test resilience indicators, such as WUE, nutrient use efficiency, soil structure and function. This analysis will use 1D (plot) or catchment scale integrated models that consider water-soil-plant system. Key variables that control WUE and reflect drought stress (several regional drought events) will be selected for

the modelling. An integrated model will be used to calculate WUE and simulate a climate series of at least 30 years in order to (1) assess the impact of drought events on the WUE of ecosystems, (2) analyse the resilience of the ecosystems with respect to their ability to recover single & multiple droughts, (3) understand the relationship between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience and develop mitigation measures for drought adverse impacts, and (4) assess strengths and weaknesses of the RI-design to derive resilience indicators.

Task 8.4 – Socio-ecological analyses of stakeholder-defined local and regional environmental challenges

The task aims to advance understanding of the impact of extreme events on socioeconomic adaptation and mitigation mechanisms and investigate gaps in policies addressing extreme events, and to use SE research to support the definition, refinement and systematic collection of SE variables. Researchers in five LTSER platforms (Alps, Braila, Cairngorms, Donana, and Eisenwurzen) will define, in consultation with local stakeholders (i.e. resource managers, farmers, tourism operators, and environmental organisations), the region's most pressing extreme event related to land use and resource management issues. We will use the socioecological research framework (Haberl et al. 2006), to characterise them in terms of interactions between social and ecosystem variables, emphasising social “presses and pulses” on the ecosystem, ecosystem response, and resultant changes in the provision of ecosystem services. We will identify the socio-economic and biogeochemical variables required for understanding socio-ecological relationships and feedbacks. Variables will be further assessed, as part of the identification and systematic collection SE data from the same five platforms. Interim and final results of this inquiry will be integrated into the upscaled policy analysis, as well as fed into the whole-systems synthesis.

Task 9.1 – Representativeness towards pan-European biodiversity pressures and trends

The Task aims to compare long-term trends and drivers of biodiversity based on low sample size, high resolution eLTER data with high sample size, low resolution non-eLTER data (based on space-for-time substitution) at a pan- European scale. We will analyse biodiversity trends and relate these trends to abiotic drivers retrieved from climate models, remote sensing, land-use maps, and socio-economic parameters (GDP, demography, etc.) using two different datasets: a) > 200 long-term biodiversity datasets from > 100 eLTER sites across Europe covering terrestrial, freshwater and coastal ecosystems and b) data compiled from non-eLTER sources (> 10,000 sites, derived from e.g. EU Water Framework or Habitat Directive). We aim to disentangle the roles of large-scale alterations in climate, air pollution and land use changes, and local changes in habitat composition, structure, function, and pollution patterns, in determining trends in biodiversity of various taxonomic groups. We will test a wide range of possible indicators, including individual species, biodiversity metrics, selected metrics of functional and phylogenetic diversity and trait composition, to determine which are best suited as indicators of long-term changes in various regions and ecosystem types. By integrating

these two datasets, we will assess the value of, and potential improvements for, the pan-European long-term time series provided by eLTER.

Task 9.2 – The Water-Climate-GHG Nexus at the pan-European scale

The Task aims to test and pilot the co-location of eLTER and ICOS RIs so as to gain new insights into the pan-European water-climate-GHG nexus, better constrain estimates of the pan-European GHG emission and carbon footprint, and develop complementary mechanistic understanding. First, we will scope the water-climate-GHG nexus across eLTER catchments.

To do so, the relevant DEIMS-SDR metadata will be updated with site PIs (including ICOS sites). In addition, large-scale modelled data (e.g. from Task 9.3, Copernicus products in WP4, ICOS products, etc.) will be identified. In collaboration with WP8 (Task 8.2), site specific estimates of GHG emission and carbon sequestration will be cross-validated against data from an independent set of eLTER sites, regionalised and up-scaled based on e.g. CORINE land cover data, climate information etc., and matched to GHG emission inventories from relevant ICOS sites. Second, a catchment-scale conceptual model of the water-climate-GHG nexus will be elaborated to better constrain estimates of the pan-European GHG emission and carbon footprint and add complementary mechanistic understanding to ICOS measurements. This will be achieved through a literature review identifying current approaches to site-scale modelling of the water-climate-GHG nexus that will then be used in a workshop with invited experts from eLTER/ICOS RIs, leaders of relevant Tasks in the project, and external researchers.

Task 9.3 – Testing eLTER network for a pan-European terrestrial ecosystem model

The Task aims to establish a validated pan-European scale terrestrial ecosystem model using eLTER network data, assess the impact of climate extremes on water related ecosystem services, and provide 30 years of reanalysed time series of hydrological fluxes. First, we will set-up the TerrSysMP (TSMP) model (with PARFLOW-CLM) for the pan-European domain at a 3 km resolution and run it for 30 years simulations. Second, we will validate the model runs against eLTER site's time series (Task 8.3). We will obtain the climatic forcing at this resolution by using a disaggregation scheme from large scale re-analyses. In addition to available time series from the eLTER network, we will use remotely sensed time series in cooperation with WP4 (e.g. SMOS, SMAP, Copernicus Hub services e.g. Sentinel data) and global soil moisture products (e.g. ESA CCI). The approach allows us to demonstrate the concept of ecosystem reanalysis for soil moisture time series, and the assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the current eLTER network design regarding the impact of climate extremes on water related ecosystem services.

Task 9.4 – Assessment of the value of eLTER for European-scale environmental policy

The Task aims to exemplify the value of eLTER research for European environmental policies through the study of aggregate knowledge derived from multiple local/regional scale studies, while simultaneously examining the relevance of local context on the efficacy of policy implementation. The Task will first carry out a cross-scale analysis of European environmental

policies (e.g., EU Water, Air Quality and Nature Directives), relevant for eLTER PLUS RC thematic diversity. The analysis will utilise a breadth of methods to address European-wide policy outcomes (e.g., regression of key variables) and the contextual depth required from the selected platforms (e.g, qualitative policy narratives). In parallel, the Task will conduct a theoretical analysis of the causal mechanisms underlying the performance of the environmental policies chosen will be carried out. Finally, based on results from the previous two steps, options for new policy developments for implementation across scales will be elaborated. To effectively close the policy making cycle, this will include an assignment of responsibilities for implementation at different institutional levels, including European and local decision makers and stakeholders. The task will also contribute to pilot data standardisation procedures, as well as specifically tailored data products (e.g., Spatial Video Geo-narratives).

8.2 Data Requirements by eLTER PLUS Science Cases

Table 15: Data requirements for long-term in-situ time series from eLTER sites

Grp	Variable name	Unit	Temp.resolution	8.1	8.2	8.3	8.4	9.1	9.2	9.3	9.4
Biodiversity	Taxonomic groups 1	occurrence/abundance/composition/biomass	annual	x				x			
Biomass	Terrestrial aboveground biomass	kg*m-2	annual		x				x		
Biomass	Terrestrial aboveground vegetation growth	kg*m-2	monthly/annual		x				x		
Biomass	Terrestrial net primary production	kgC*m-2	daily/monthly/annual		x	x	x		x	x	x
Biomass	Terrestrial gross primary production	kgC*m-2	daily/monthly/annual		x	x	x		x	x	x
Biomass	Leaf area Index (LAI)	unitless	daily/monthly/annual		x	x		x	x	x	
Biomass	Tissue (Leaf) C and N content	%	annual		x				x		
Biomass	Aboveground litterfall	kg*m-2	monthly/annual		x				x		
Biomass	Belowground (soil) litterfall	kg*m-2	monthly/annual		x				x		
Climate	Air temperature	°C	30 min	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Climate	Precipitation	mm	30 min	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Climate	Relative air humidity	%	30 min		x	x			x	x	
Climate	Wind speed / Wind direction	m*s-1, °	30 min				x			x	
Climate	Surface atmospheric pressure	mbar	30 min				x			x	
Climate	Photosynthetic Active Radiation	W*m-2 or PPFD	30 min				x	x		x	
Climate	Direct incoming short wave radiation	W*m-2	30 min				x	x		x	
Climate	Reflected short wave radiation	W*m-2	30 min				x			x	
Climate	Diffused long-wave radiation from the sky	W*m-2	30 min				x			x	
Climate	Diffused long-wave radiation from the surface	W*m-2	30 min				x			x	
Atmospheric deposition	Bulk NH4-N, NO3-N, Ntot deposition in precipitation	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Atmospheric deposition	Bulk P deposition in precipitation	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Atmospheric deposition	Bulk K deposition in precipitation	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Atmospheric deposition	Bulk NH4-N, NO3-N, Ntot deposition in canopy throughfall (forests)	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Atmospheric deposition	Bulk P deposition in canopy throughfall (forests)	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Atmospheric deposition	Bulk K deposition in canopy throughfall (forests)	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Atmospheric deposition	NH4-N, NO3-N, Ntot deposition in stemflow (forests)	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Atmospheric deposition	P deposition in stemflow (forests)	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Atmospheric deposition	K deposition in stemflow (forests)	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Atmospheric deposition	Dry deposition of Nitrogen	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Soil-atmosphere exchange	gas Eddy covariance flux data product (compatible with ICOS L2, Ameriflux, Fluxnet)	various	various			x					x
Soil-atmosphere exchange	gas Soil CO2 flux	gC*m-2	daily/monthly/annual		x				x		
Soil-atmosphere exchange	gas Soil CH4 flux	gC*m-2	daily/monthly/annual		x				x		
Soil-atmosphere exchange	gas Soil N2O, NO, NOx flux	gC*m-2	daily/monthly/annual		x				x		

Grp	Variable name	Unit	Temp.resolution	8.1	8.2	8.3	8.4	9.1	9.2	9.3	9.4
Air quality	Ozone concentration	ppm	30 min		x				x		
Air quality	NOx concentration	mg*m-3	30 min		x				x		
Air quality	NH3 concentration	mg*m-3	30 min		x				x		
Soil climate	Soil temperature	°C	30 min		x	x		x	x	x	
Soil climate	Soil water content	Vol%	30 min	x	x	x		x	x	x	
Solid soil chemistry	Soil organic C content (per horizon)	mg*kg-1	annual	x	x	x		x	x	x	
Solid soil chemistry	Soil total N content (per horizon)	mg*kg-1	annual	x	x	x		x	x	x	
Solid soil chemistry	Soil total P content (per horizon)	mg*kg-1	annual	x	x	x		x	x	x	
Solid soil chemistry	Soil total K content (per horizon)	mg*kg-1	annual	x							
Solid soil chemistry	Soil pH (in H2O/KCl/CaCl2) (per horizon)	unitless	annual	x	x	x		x	x	x	
Solid soil chemistry	Soil cation exchange capacity (per horizon)	cmolc*kg-1	annual	x	x	x		x	x	x	
Solid soil chemistry	Soil base saturation (per horizon)	%	annual		x	x		x	x	x	
Soil water	NH4-N, NO3-N, DON concentration	mg*l-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Soil water	NH4-N, NO3-N, DON leaching	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Soil water	DOC concentration	mg*l-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Soil water	DOC leaching	kg*ha-1	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Soil water	Percolation	mm	monthly		x	x			x	x	
Runoff, streams and standing water	TOC, DOC concentration	mg*l-1	monthly or higher frequency	x				x	x		
Runoff, streams and standing water	Ntot, NH4-N, NO3-N concentration	mg*l-1	monthly (or finer)	x		x		x	x	x	
Runoff, streams and standing water	P concentration	mg*l-1	monthly (or finer)	x		x		x	x	x	
Runoff, streams and standing water	Cation concentrations	mg*l-1	monthly (or finer)	x		x			x		
Runoff, streams and standing water	Anion concentrations	mg*l-1	monthly (or finer)			x			x		
Runoff, streams and standing water	pH value	unitless	monthly (or finer)	x		x		x			
Runoff, streams and standing water	Conductivity	mS*m-1	monthly (or finer)	x		x		x		x	
Runoff, streams and standing water	Discharge	l*s-1	monthly (or finer)	x		x		x		x	
Runoff, streams and standing water	Water temperature	°C	monthly (or finer)	x				x			
Runoff, streams and standing water	Pesticides	mg*l-1	monthly (or finer)	x				x			
Runoff, streams and standing water	Transparency	m	monthly (or finer)	x				x			
Groundwater	Groundwater table height	cm	monthly (or finer)		x	x			x	x	
Groundwater	Cation concentrations	mg*l-1	monthly (or finer)	x		x			x		
Groundwater	Anion concentrations	mg*l-1	monthly (or finer)			x			x		
Land use	N, P, K fertilisation	kg*m-2	annual		x	x		x	x	x	
Land use	Liming	kg*m-2	annual		x	x		x	x	x	

Grp	Variable name	Unit	Temp.resolution	8.1	8.2	8.3	8.4	9.1	9.2	9.3	9.4
Land use	Pesticides	kg*m-2	annual		x	x		x	x	x	
Land use	Grazing timing, stocking intensity, animal	time*yr-1, LU*ha-1	annual		x	x	x		x	x	x
Land use	Crop, grassland harvesting	kg*m-2	annual		x	x	x		x	x	x
Land use	Forest planting, thinning, clearcut	number/m ³ *ha-1	annual		x	x	x		x	x	x
Land use	Irrigation timing, amount	m ³ *event	annual		x	x			x	x	
Land use	Visitors	number	annual				x				x
Socio-economy	Gross domestic product	EUR	decadal	x			x				x
Socio-economy	Governance structure and character	descriptive	decadal				x				x
Socio-economy	Demography	tbd	decadal	x			x				x
Socio-economy	Property ownership/laws/institutions	tbd	decadal				x				x

Table 16: Data requirements for plot or site scale data from eLTER sites

Grp	Variable name	Unit	Temp.resolution	8.1	8.2	8.3	8.4	9.1	9.2	9.3	9.4
Topography	elevation, slope, aspect	m, °, °			x				x		
Vegetation	Forest stand age	yr			x	x			x	x	
Soil physics	Soil type	categories		x	x	x			x	x	
Soil physics	Parent material (geology)	categories		x	x	x			x	x	
Soil physics	Soil bulk density	g*cm-3			x	x			x	x	
Soil physics	Soil depth (per horizon)	cm			x	x			x	x	
Soil physics	Soil fractions (Water stable aggregate fractionation)	% per fraction				x				x	
Soil physics	Soil texture	categories			x	x			x	x	
Soil physics	Soil stone content (>2mm)	%			x	x			x	x	
Soil physics	Soil water retention capacity (water retention curves; field capacity, water saturation, wilting point)	mm*cm-1			x	x			x	x	
Soil physics	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	m*s-1			x	x			x	x	
Land cover	Land cover	categories		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Land use	Crop type	categories			x				x		
Land use	Fire regime	categories		x							
Land use	Forest management	categories									x
Land use	Land use (historic)	descriptive					x			x	x
Land use	Land use change	descriptive					x			x	x
Habitat diversity	River Habitat Survey (RHS) information	categories		x							
Habitat diversity	Habitat map/list	categories							x		

Table 17: Data requirements for remote sensing data

Grp	Variable name	Unit	8.1	8.2	8.3	8.4	9.1	9.2	9.3	9.4
Remote sensing	Productivity (NDVI)		x							
Remote sensing	Phenology/Seasonality		x							
Land cover	CORINE Land cover (or similar)	categories	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

Table 18: Data requirements for socio-ecological data

Input variables	Variable [txt]	Specific method requirements [txt]	Minumum Time Span [yrs]	Time range [date]	Temporal resolution [txt]	Spatial resolution [rxt]	Data format [txt]
Population							
	Population age	EU census	since start of record	all	annual	smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	CSV
	Population current activity status	EU census	since start of record	all	annual	see above	CSV
	Population Occupation	EU census	since start of record	all	annual	see above	CSV
	Population Industry	EU census	since start of record	all	annual	see above	CSV
	Population status of employment	EU census	since start of record	all	annual	see above	CSV
	Population Education attainment	EU census	since start of record	all	annual	see above	CSV
	Population Place of Birth	EU census	since start of record	all	annual	see above	CSV
	Population Housing arrangement	EU census	since start of record	all	annual	see above	CSV
Land cover and land cover change							
	Land use (historic)	RS	since start of record	all	decadal	30 m2 to 1 m2	GIS polygons/raster
	Land cover	CORINE	since start of record	all	As available	25 hectares (ha) for areal phenomena and a minimum width of 100 m for linear phenomena	GIS polygons/raster
	Land use change	CORINE	since start of record	all	As available	25 hectares (ha) for areal phenomena and a minimum width of 100 m for linear phenomena	GIS polygons/raster
	Land use	national agricultural and forest statistics		c. 19th century to present	annual	national / provincial	CSV, pdf
	Land use	archival cadastral records		18th-19th centuries	sporadic	source-specific (local)	on paper, georeferenced in rare cases

Input variables Variable [txt]	Specific method requirements [txt]	Minumum Time Span [yrs]	Time range [date]	Temporal resolution [txt]	Spatial resolution [rxt]	Data format [txt]
Land cover	Orthophotos		20th century	sporadic	local	images, sometimes georeferenced
Governance and stakeholder						
Governance structure and character	Governance categories (to be determined)	Commensurate with demographic data	all	decadal	political/administrative units	qualitative
Sense of Place / Nature connectedness	Protocol in development	From start of eLTER-PLUS	all	annual	smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	Contingent on methodology
Stakeholder engagement process indicators and profile of engaged stakeholders	Protocol in development	From start of eLTER-PLUS	all	annual	See above	Contingent on methodology
Platform characteristics						
Platform characteristics	Protocol predetermined by DEIMS	From start of eLTER-PLUS	all	5 year	See above	Registered in DEIMS
Property ownership/laws/institutions	Narrative/categorization	since start of record	all	decadal	See above	Narrative, categories
Ecosystem services profile	Protocol needs to be developed	From start records	all	annual	correlating with land use map or population data	GIS polygons/raster + quantitative data (CSV)
Main environmental parameters (precipitation, temperature)	Derived from LTER site data (DEIMS?)	since start of record	all	annual	smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	Depends on variable
Ecological data (productivity, biodiversity; data systematically collected in associated LTER sites)	Derived from LTER site data (DEIMS?)	since start of record	all	annual	correlating with land use map	Depends on variable
NUTS3 and Local Administrative Units (LAU) spatial databases	EUROSTAT	Current version 2016	2016	Every 3 years	16667:40:00	Different file formats
Number of tourists/visitors to protected areas	Local Park Managers	since start of record	all	monthly	Per protected area	CSV
Per capita income / GDP per capita	EUROSTAT	since start of record	all	annual	Ideally per NUT3	CSV
Resource use						
Resource use (biomass, construction, iron/steel, fossil fuels), trade of resources	Protocol needs to be developed	since start of record	all	annual	smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	

Input variables Variable [txt]	Specific method requirements [txt]	Minumum Time Span [yrs]	Time range [date]	Temporal resolution [txt]	Spatial resolution [rxt]	Data format [txt]
Infrastructure physically and in terms of services available	Protocol needs to be developed	since start of record	all	10 years	???	GIS
Time use	EU census?	since start of record	all	10 years	societal units (household types)	

Table 19: Data requirements for socio-ecological data (additional data)

Input variables Variable [txt]	Specific method requirements [txt]	Minumum Time Span [yrs]	Time range [date]	Temporal resolution [txt]	Spatial resolution [rxt]	Data format [txt]
Population consumption statistics	EU census	since start of record	all	annual	smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	CSV
Subsidies programs / schemes	FADN EU database / National statistics			annual/every 3,5,10 years	smallest administrative spatial units available (Nuts2/Nuts3)	xlsx/csv/txt
Records of important land users (e.g., forest enterprises)	Historical statistics	18th-19th century				
Relevant regional actors and initiatives (NGO's, civil society groups, etc.)	Stakeholder analysis					
Time use	EU census?	since start of record	all	10 years	societal units (household types)	
Wellbeing information of population	statistics and interviews					
mobility information: accessibility indicators, means of transport						
mobility: distances travelled (locals vs tourists)						
Living conditions in dwellings: m2 per person; thermal quality;	protocol needs to be developed					
Basic services provision: health & education	protocol needs to be developed					
Resource use (energy carriers, electricity, biomass, construction, iron/steel, fossil fuels),	protocol needs to be specified; for example from material and energy flow analysis	since start of record	all	annual	smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	
Industrial use of biomass (biorefinery, etc.)						
Physical infrastructure networks	protocol to be specified, ideally description in various physical	since start of record	all	annual	spatially explicit	GIS

Input variables Variable [txt]	Specific method requirements [txt]	Minumum Time Span [yrs]	Time range [date]	Temporal resolution [txt]	Spatial resolution [rxt]	Data format [txt]
	dimensions (km, m2, ...)) for a stock-driven "bottom-up" modelling					
Buildings and other structures	protocol to be specified, ideally description in various physical dimensions (km, m2, ...)) for a stock-driven "bottom-up" modelling	since start of record	all	annual	spatially explicit	GIS
Roads, Railways, settlement areas	Open streetmaps		all	annual	Spatially explicit	GIS
Regional supply level						
livestock (livestock units)	FADN EU database / National statistics	since start of record	all	annual	smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	xlsx/csv/txt
Lifestock feed management	FADN EU database / National statistics	since start of record	all		smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	xlsx/csv/txt
Agricultural products	FADN EU database / National statistics	since start of record	all	annual	smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	xlsx/csv/txt
irrigation management	EU FADN	since start of record	all	annual	smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	xlsx/csv/txt
fertilizer input	EU FADN	since start of record	all	annual	smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	xlsx/csv/txt
harvest (cropland, grassland, forest) (t/ha)	EU FADN	since start of record	all	annual	smallest administrative spatial units available (municipality?)	xlsx/csv/txt

8.3 ICT Requirements Interview template Data users

In the first iteration targeted interviews were done with researchers. The interviews aimed to capture the researchers' perspective as data users concerning both the context of eLTER Research Challenges and their scientific experience in general. The interviews were semi-structured and covered a wide range of questions around data management processes. Some of the questions were technical while others concerned policies, and usually it was difficult to answer all questions, as very few people have the skills to answer all kinds of questions regarding data stewardship and management.

In the following the structure of the interview is listed.

1 Acquisition of data

- 1.1 What domains of data will you use in your research (e.g. biodiversity, environmental observation, census data, earth observation)?
- 1.2 What data sources or repositories do you use (e.g. eLTER, Pangea, EUDAT, Zenodo, European Statistics, own research and monitoring, documents and reports) to retrieve the data?
- 1.3 What tools and services do you use to discover desired but unknown data and/or long term time series (e.g. personal contact, search engines, metadata catalogues)?
- 1.4 What metadata format / catalogue service is used to document the data and where do you find the metadata (e.g. in-file metadata)?
- 1.5 What are the most important topics to search for datasets (e.g. location, parameter, length time series)?
- 1.6 How do you access the data (e.g. download, email, API, service)?
- 1.7 What is the format of the data (e.g. flat files, databases, data services)?
- 1.8 Are vocabularies and code lists used in the data (e.g. parameter names, taxonomy) and are they publicly available?
- 1.9 How would you cite the data used?
- 1.10 Does the data you use have a unique identifier (like UUID) or does it have a resolvable, persistent identifier (PID), like DOI, ePID handle, or URN)?
- 1.11 Are identifiers for other purposes than data (e.g. Site, instrument, creator, sample, species, parameters) included and are they resolvable (e.g. PID), too?
- 1.12 What types of licenses are used for published datasets and are they publicly available and machine-readable?
- 1.13 Do you use data requiring GDPR processes to be taken into account ?
- 1.14 Do you have a consent management implemented for data collection?

1.15 Do you use other kind of sensitive data (e.g. personal information, locations of rare animals or plants)?

2 Processing of data

2.1 What processes will you implement to prepare and clean the data (e.g. quality control, structural harmonisation) prior to the data analysis?

2.2 What kind of tools and infrastructures will be used to prepare and clean the data and how could that be supported by eLTER?

2.3 What kind of code lists and vocabularies do you need in order to harmonise the input data and what kind services do you need?

2.4 What information needs to be kept to ensure reproducibility?

2.5 Is reproducibility information stored and linked with datasets?

2.6 What will you do to analyse the (long term) site data together with other data sources?

2.7 What kind of tools and infrastructures (e.g. DataLab, EGI, DIAS) will be used to analyse the data and how could that be supported by eLTER?

2.8 What information needs to be kept to ensure reproducibility?

2.9 Is reproducibility information stored and linked with datasets ?

3 Publication of research results and data

3.1 What kind of result will be published as output of your analysis (e.g. paper, aggregated data, model)?

3.2 Where will you envisage to publish the research output?

3.3 Where will the data and/or documentation be published?

3.4 How should we ensure persistent linking between these in your opinion?

3.5 Can the data in the repository be accessed by using a public web link (e.g. API)?

3.6 Is the description of the access mode (e.g. API documentation) available publicly?

3.7 Are the resulting data open access and what license (e.g. CC-BY 4.0) will be applied for the data?

3.8 Do you publish data requiring GDPR processes or special category data (e.g. data on a living individual, video recordings, audio recordings) to be taken into account?

3.9 Do you publish other kinds of sensitive data (e.g. locations of rare animals or plants, pollution events, location of sampling plots) where data protection processes need to be taken into account?

4 Documentation of research results and data

4.1 What kind information in the metadata is needed to ensure discoverability and reusability of the resulting data output (e.g. location, methods, parameters)?

4.2 Does the metadata model use some generally known schema and is it described somewhere?

4.3 Can the end user compare to other data with the help of metadata (e.g. description of methods used)?

4.4 Can you trace the provenance of the data and which additional elements should be included in the metadata (e.g. station)?

4.5 What code lists and vocabularies do you currently use to document and describe your data (e.g. EnvThes for keywords, parameters)?

4.6 What are the gaps in current vocabularies / code lists that stop you documenting the data (e.g. standard measurement methods)?

5 Data curation and long term data management

5.1 How long should the data be stored?

5.2 Do you have a long term data curation plan (host data repository, updating formats, versioning)?

5.3 How do you envisage to provide information on versioning of the data on metadata level using relations e.g. IsNewVersionOf, IsPreviousVersionOf, etc.)?

6 Services required for Community support

6.1 What kind of tools do you expect from the eLTER Information System (e.g. catalogues, data visualisations tools, code support for R / Python, etc.)

6.2 What kind of support are you expecting from the eLTER Information Management (e.g. tutorials, webinars, training)?

6.3 What other kinds of services functionalities do you expect (e.g. must-have, nice-to-have)?

8.4 ICT Requirements Interview template Data providers

In the first iteration targeted interviews were done with data providers. The interviews aimed to represent the consolidated practices of the data providers and their background in using eLTER data management services. The interviews were semi-structured and covered a wide range of questions around data management processes. Some of the questions were technical while others concerned policies, and usually it was difficult to answer all questions, as very few people have the skills to answer all kinds of questions regarding data stewardship and management.

In the following the structure of the interview is listed.

1 General questions

- 1.1 What data repositories, data catalogues or data services do you operate/provide (please provide links)?
- 1.2 What data are held and shared in the repository / data infrastructure?
- 1.3 How are the data held (database, flat files, data services, etc)?
- 1.4 Is the data in repositories unique or can it be recollected if needed?
- 1.5 Are the data available through the eLTER Information System? If no, why not?

2 Metadata and data provision

- 2.1 Is there any documentation describing the data (e.g. metadata, data paper)?
- 2.2 What metadata format / catalogue service is used to document the data and where do you find the metadata (e.g. in-file metadata, metadata standard)?
- 2.3 Are the metadata publicly online available (e.g. metadata catalogue)? If yes, please provide a link.
- 2.4 Do the data have a persistent resolvable identifiers (e.g. DOI)?
- 2.5 How should the data be cited?
- 2.6 Are there any licensing conditions for using the data?
- 2.7 Are the data quality controlled and how are the QC procedures documented (e.g. including level of quality control and procedure in the metadata)?
- 2.8 Is there documentation or guidelines on the QC procedure (e.g. offline or online) available? If online, please provide a link.
- 2.9 What kind of code lists and vocabularies do you use in order to document and describe your data (e.g. keywords, parameter names)?
- 2.10 Are the additional FAIR principles implemented in your services (not addressed above, e.g. provenance)? How?

2.11 What kind of support do you expect from the eLTER Information System?

3 Services and processes (on current or target architecture)

3.1 What services (e.g. metadata/data API, QA workflows) do you provide and to whom?

3.2 What services provided by other service providers (e.g. EUDAT, EGI, EOSC) do you use?

3.3 Are there any (free and open) existing visualisation/analysis tools available for the data you are providing?

3.4 What kind of analysis tasks are done for data (high level description only)?

3.5 What kind of resources (e.g. cloud computing, Jupyter) do you use for data analysis purposes?

3.6 What kind of network requirements do you have for your operations ?

3.7 What services and processes could be provided by eLTER to assist your data workflows?

4 Authentication and Security

4.1 What kind of Authentication, Authorization, and Identification technology (AAI) does your organization use?

4.2 How is the security of the data ensured? Are the data backed up or replicated to other locations?

5 Organisation of data management

5.1 What is the strategic vision in terms of data provision? (shortly, or give a link)?

5.2 Do you have governance to ensure good data management? Are Data Management Plans and Data Policy available and shared? Are data rights and licensing clear?

5.3 Which stakeholders do you serve?

5.4 Is there an organization (e.g. Data Centre) for data management and what is the mission of the organization (shortly, or give a link)?

5.5 If yes, which organizational form (foundation, ERIC, national research entity, ...) is implemented?

5.6 If yes, is the enterprise architecture of the organization described somewhere?

5.7 Do you operate or use a long-term data repository?

5.8 If yes, do you have any certificates or do you plan to get a certification for the data repository (e.g. CoreTrustSeal)?

8.5 ICT Requirements List of User Stories

8.5.1 Research community

eLTER-US-R01	As a researcher I want to document the provenance of the data I have uploaded, so that my research is valid.
Description: Adding minimal metadata including an identifier to the dataset is necessary to keep track of ownership and the origin of the data. Existing metadata or PIDs should be reused avoiding duplication of information.	
Comments: A source URL recommended if PID is missing. Might contain importing and exporting metadata. Using the INSPIRE (ISO19115) metadata element <i>Lineage</i> , which is only a free text field, would create potential problems as cascades of related datasets could not be stored in a structured way (e.g. PROV-graph, preceding version).	
Type: PIDs, metadata, interoperability, ingest, relations/links, Reusable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DataLabs	
eLTER-US-R02	As a researcher I need tools that support data collection and creation, so that my data is stored in a common format and I can use shared workflows.
Description: Data and metadata should be born FAIR if possible, as standardised and harmonised as feasible. Shared standards, formats, tools and protocols enable this.	
Comments: This is a very general requirement, most relevant is probably the notion about formats and quality control workflows, which might relate to data (files) as well as metadata. Similar to eLTER-US-D02	
Type: workflow management, formats, relations/links, ingest, Reusable	
Related components: DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DataLabs	
eLTER-US-R03	As a researcher I want to compare datasets, so that I can assess them.
Description: As a researcher I want to compare how different dataset suit my needs, so that I can assess them. This includes access to interoperable and rich metadata, good search functionalities as well as tools like visualisation.	
Comments: Comparing and assessing datasets is done both via metadata that includes information about acquisition and provenance and studying the data itself	
Type: metadata, UI, Reusable	
Related components: Data labs for data analysis. DEIMS and Digital Asset Registry for metadata	

eLTER-US-R04	As a researcher I want to do data conversions into recommended formats, so that I can use eLTER tools.
Description: Data conversions for data from different sources into recommended common formats are sometimes necessary to create interoperable data and to use eLTER tools and apply existing analytical workflows.	
Comments: This needs the definition of common input formats (e.g. ICOS, ICPs) to be transformed and harmonised according to specific criteria. This not only includes structural harmonisation but also semantic harmonisation both in terms of variable naming and content (e.g. species taxonomy). Also metadata is relevant in this user story.	
Type: formats, ingest, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable	
Related components: DataLabs, EnvThes, Semantics	

eLTER-US-R05	As a researcher I want to publish a compiled dataset with provenance metadata, so that I can cite it.
Description: When new datasets are created by combining existing dataset there is a need for provenance metadata, so that citation can be done giving credit to the source dataset. The compiled dataset is the result of an analytical workflow which is published and shared with the scientific community.	
Comments: Based on analytical workflows aggregated data products (level 3) are generated by the user and shared with the scientific community. This includes also provenance information on the ingested data and the process applied to the data. This could e.g. be the result of a scientific analysis or a EEV data product generated by the eLTER RI community.	
Type: metadata, PIDs, publishing, relations/links, Findable, Reusable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry (once the RI is established and can mint DOIs), EUDAT, CDN	

eLTER-US-R06	As a researcher I want to manage different versions of my data, so that I can track updates and errors.
Description: To ensure reproducibility and to track data updates and errors, dataset versions need to be kept and tracked. The information on preceding versions of the data should be available and visible as provenance.	
Comments: versioning of the data is one of the core functions for the eLTER Information System in future. This can be supported by issuing PIDs to the different datasets in the infrastructure and a clear PID policy and management. An issue to be solved is versioning of dynamic data series as provided by the OGC SOS services applied in the eLTER context. Version history should point to the latest version of the data including information on preceding versions of the dataset. Citation should always be unambiguous.	
Type: metadata, relations/links, workflows, PIDs, Reusable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DataLabs	

eLTER-US-R07	As a researcher I want to manage different versions of my code, so that I can track updates and errors.
Description: To ensure reproducibility and to track data updates and errors, code versions need to be kept and tracked. The information on preceding versions of the code should be available and visible as provenance.	

Comments: The code to run data analytics should be shared together with the data. Code should be available to the wider scientific community and be versioned to ensure the tracking of updates. This is needed to implement the re-usability and reproducibility of the data in the eLTER context.
Type: metadata, relations/links, workflows, Reusable
Related components: GitHub, GitLab, Data labs

eLTER-US-R08	As a researcher I want to contact the data provider, so that I can validate the suitability of the dataset for my research.
Description: The researcher needs to get in touch with the data provider for different reasons (e.g. to get additional information about the dataset, to request the raw data).	
Comments: Sufficient information to assess the fitness for use of the data used should be included in the descriptive metadata. This includes e.g. the applied protocols, the workflows conducted to generate the datasets or the provenance of data used to compile the dataset. In addition, contact to the data provider should be possible to answer additional questions or when the license requires to interact with the owner to retrieve the dataset. This also includes update and versioning of metadata for the datasets.	
Type: metadata, workflows, user contact, Reusable	
Related components: DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset registry	

eLTER-US-R09	As a researcher I want to use common semantic artefacts when I document my data, so that my data is interoperable.
Description: Common semantic artefacts on different levels of the data documentation and provision process as well as when publishing data make the (meta)data interoperable and enhances findability. Integrated semantic artefacts also make metadata creation easier by offering suggestions when annotating.	
Comments: Common vocabularies are used to not only annotate the data (e.g. keyword tagging for discovery) but also used in the data (e.g. variable naming) to ensure semantic interoperability of the datasets shared. The annotation process on both levels needs to be supported by the data infrastructure and the tools provided. This includes also the sharing and provision of code lists (e.g. species taxonomies, land use taxonomies, etc.) used as data values. The underlying and supported codelists should be openly available and provide a persistent identification of the terms (e.g. PID, URL).	
Type: metadata, interoperability, semantics, PIDs, Interoperable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry, CDN, EnvThes, DEIMS-SDR	

eLTER-US-R10	As a researcher I want to contact the service provider, to apply for more resources.
Description: The user of the data has to be able to contact the service provider, to apply for more resources like storage quota or HPC resources, or with other service requests.	
Comments: This process will be depending on the use policy of the service.	
Type: user contact	

Related components: DataLab, CDN, HPC service providers

eLTER-US-R11	As a researcher I want to publish my outputs, so that I can adhere to funder requirements.
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Description: Researchers need to publish outputs in an open and trusted repository, so that they can adhere to funder requirements or requirements by Journals in the cause of scientific publication. A citation of the data should be possible.

Comments: Quality checked datasets resulting from eLTER sites or analytical workflows should be shared via trusted repositories and services implementing the FAIR principles. The eLTER Information System and Architecture needs to comply with this requirement by providing the metadata, data stores and data services as well as related documentation of the data (e.g. provenance). In addition, this also implies the assignment of a common data policy ensuring the legal interoperability of data and data products. Data publication needs to include the publication and sharing of metadata, datasets and related workflows. This could also include for instance integration with OpenAIRE and ORCID.

Type: workflows, metadata, PIDs, relations/links, data license, publishing

Related components: Digital Asset Registry or EUDAT for DOIs; Data labs for workflows; DEIMS-SDR and Digital Asset Registry for metadata

eLTER-US-R12	As a researcher I want training, so that I can use the tools efficiently.
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Description: Users need training, so that they can use the tools efficiently.

Comments: This includes the provision of demo environments, training datasets, or example code to run and test the eLTER Information System and Architecture. Tutorial material should be provided as well as direct support by the central services of the eLTER RI.

Type: training, webinar, code examples, direct support, user contact

Related components: DataLabs, training instances, git,

eLTER-US-R13	As a researcher I need support with optimizing my code, so that I can be as fast as the next group.
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Description: To enhance and support research and the use of both common and project resources, optimizing code is essential support.

Comments: who should provide this? Could there be a user community platform for peer support?

Type: user contact, training,

Related components: DataLabs, HPC

eLTER-US-R14	As a researcher I want to manage my workflows and share them, so that I get more citations
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Description: Managing and sharing workflows are important for the research process. Publishing workflows is a prerequisite for reproducible research and gives researchers more visibility.

Comments: This relies on the assumption that what applies to data applies to code regarding credit
Type: PIDs, workflows, publishing
Related components: Data labs, git

eLTER-US-R15	As a researcher I want documentation to be automatic when possible, so that the metadata and links are standardized
Description: Documentation should be automatic when possible, so that the metadata and links are standardized and manual work minimised.	
Comments: similar to eLTER-US-D04	
Type: PID, semantic artefacts, workflows, metadata, interoperability, provenance, Findable, Interoperable	
Related components: DataLabs, Digital Asset Registry, CDN, DEIMS, DIP	

eLTER-US-R16	As a researcher I want to publish all my outputs, so that I can get cited.
Description: Researchers want to publish as much as possible, not only articles, so that they get cited as much as possible. The FAIR principles and Open Science support the idea that the research should be as transparent as possible.	
Comments: The publishing of the outputs of a research life cycle including the workflows should be supported by the eLTER Information System. This includes recording of the provenance and the workflows (e.g. including quality control) applied to the data to generate the output (e.g. published datasets). Persistent identification is needed in order to allow the citation and use of data by other communities.	
Type: PID, metadata, publishing, workflows, data, PID/DOI, provenance, Findable, Interoperable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR (site reference)	

eLTER-US-R17	As a researcher I want to link my outputs, so that my research is reproducible.
Description: To support findability and reproducibility in research all related outputs and elements of the research should be linked in a trustworthy and rich manner.	
Comments: this can maybe be combined with eLTER-US-R16?	
Type: metadata, PID, relations/links, Interoperable	
Related components: Data labs, Digital Asset Registry	

eLTER-US-R18	As a researcher I want to control how my data is stored, so that I can influence the retention time.
Description: Researchers want to control how their data is stored, so that they can influence the retention time. Not all data needs to be kept forever and eLTER should support data lifecycle planning.	
Comments: This will need to be addressed in the RI Data Policy and the retention/access policies of the Digital Asset Registry. We are aiming for an open data access policy so this will need to be carefully considered.	
Type: metadata, access, DMP, rights management, Accessible	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry, CDN	

eLTER-US-R19	As a researcher I want to control the access to my sensitive research data, so that I can comply with GDPR and good scientific practice.
Description: GDPR and good scientific practice require restricted access and authorizations to some sensitive datasets. Someone then has to manage the rights and access.	
Comments: This will need to be addressed in the RI Data Policy and the retention/access policies of the Digital Asset Registry. In addition workflows to ensure anonymisation and pseudo-anonymisation of the data needs to be provided in order to ensure GDPR compliance. Linking to repositories (e.g. social-science and humanities) for interview data should be considered. Similar to eLTER-US-D11.	
Type: metadata, access, rights management, workflows, Accessible	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry, CDN	

eLTER-US-R20	As a researcher I want to search/discover datasets provided by the eLTER RI and eLTER network to be used in research.
Description: All metadata on datasets and data products can be searched and accessed from a central catalogue and links to the datasets and data products are provided. Relevant meta information to ensure the use and re-use of the data should be provided.	
Comments: Basic metadata e.g. on the location, variables observed, length of time series, spatial coverage, or taxonomic coverage would be key aspects in the search for data. Relevant information needs to be ingested from available catalogues and should be provided for the search. This also should include the discovery of the related site information. Also linked to eLTER-US-D20	
Type: metadata, access, workflows, semantics, Findable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR	

8.5.2 Data provider community

eLTER-US-D01	As a data provider, I need support with creating a good data management plan, so that all data is compliant, interoperable and of good quality.
Description: Clear common data management policies, organisational and legal interoperability are needed to support FAIR born data within the eLTER. The implementation should then be supported by training efforts and templates as well as other support to implement good practices.	

Comments: This is not directly in the scope of the tasks at hand, but could be supported by for instance offering clear terms of use (e.g. intellectual rights on data or licenses applied) and requiring links to DMP etc. in metadata for dataset, projects, platforms and similar entities.	
Type: training, DMP, user contact, data licenses, Accessible, Reusable	
Related components: eLTER, Data governance,	
eLTER-US-D02	As a data provider, I want to have access to common protocols, so that datasets are harmonized as early as possible in the data lifecycle.
Description: Protocols should ideally be published in repositories that provide metadata, version control and PIDs. Protocols are workflows to collect the data that include manual steps. They can also include for instance handbooks, guidelines, a structured interview script, survey/data templates or similar tools to capture data or observation. Shared repositories or discovery services could be considered.	
Comments: similar to eLTER-US-R02. Assuring comparison among research activities is crucial in the development of the eLTER RI. Common protocols and organization of dataset will allow to increase the reproducibility as well as the integration of data across monitoring and experimental facilities.	
Type: workflows, provenance metadata, data standard, Interoperable, Reusable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry	
eLTER-US-D03	As a data provider, I want to upload my dataset, so that it can be stored in a secure way.
Description: Data should be archived and ingested to common defined data products within eLTER. This includes the upload as well as the documentation of the data. When uploading data a PID, either existing or new, should be added to the dataset to enable tracking of the data in the eLTER Information System. Also, check-sum management should be part of this process.	
Comments: Uploading data is only one step of the ingest process, and should preferably not be considered without context. The focus should maybe be put on the secure storage, i.e. access management and data security (of which metadata is an important part)	
Type: ingest, access, rights management, storage, PID, provenance, integrity	
Related components: CDN	
eLTER-US-D04	As a data provider, I want to create metadata with minimal effort, so that I can publish rich metadata.
Description: Metadata creation should be supported by automation wherever possible. This should include suggestions, auto-fill in, integrated semantic artefacts etc. All categories of metadata should be considered.	
Comments: Existing information e.g. from observation protocols (if documented in machine readable way) could be extracted as well as information from the documented sites and pre-filled for the metadata. Workflows to enable that should be developed. Similar to eLTER-US-R01, eLTER-US-R15, and also related to eLTER-US-D05.	
Type: ingest, metadata, workflows, provenance, semantic artefacts, Findable, Interoperable	

Related components: Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR

eLTER-US-D05	As a data provider, I want to import metadata, so that I don't have to type or copy-paste each value manually.
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Description: As a data provider, I would like to use a standardized API to push the metadata or I would like the system to harvest my catalog through OGC CSW standardized webservice.

Existing metadata from local systems (e.g. national network catalogue or site level catalogue) should be ingested into the central metadata catalogue without or with minor manual interaction. Some technical, structural and administrative metadata can also be autogenerated.

Comments: The same standards as the eLTER-US-D06 export use case should be considered for importing metadata (i.e ISO 19115, EML). Also consider the data itself: It should be possible to harvest data through OGC SOS standardized web service. Similar to eLTER-US-R01, related to eLTER-US-D04

Type: ingest, metadata, workflows, provenance, PIDs, Findable, Reusable

Related components: Digital Asset Registry

eLTER-US-D06	As a data provider, I want to export metadata, so that I don't have to type or copy-paste each value manually.
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Description: Metadata should be re-used and provided according to different standards (e.g. INSPIRE, EML) based on the provided metadata. Transformation scripts according to different standards should be developed.

Comments: Related to eLTER-US-D10

Type: download, workflows, provenance, PIDs

Related components: Digital Asset Registry

eLTER-US-D07	As a data provider, I want to choose which semantic artefacts I use, so that I can use relevant subject headings and terminology.
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Description: This could include both integrated semantic artefacts, uploading semantic artefacts or linking/using them via widget etc

Comments: Similar to eLTER-US-R09

Type: semantic artefacts, UI, metadata, publishing, Interoperable

Related components: Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR, semantic services

eLTER-US-D08	As a data provider, I want to link my dataset to instruments, so that provenance and format are clear and unambiguous
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Description: Information on the instruments (e.g. sensors) and the protocols are important to ensure reusability of the data. This information should be linked to the data being generated on these protocols and sensors deployed.

Comments: related to eLTER-US-D17
Type: instruments, provenance, metadata, PID, semantics, Interoperable, Reusable
Related components: DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset Registry

eLTER-US-D09	As a data provider, I want to have a rich data model, so that I can express the organization of my datasets in a clear way.
Description: The metadata model should offer collections, hierarchies and a rich set of relations between data objects.	
Comments: DCAT	
Type: links, metadata, Accessible, Interoperable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry	

eLTER-US-D10	As a data provider, I want there to be a citation mechanism, so that I get credit for my work.
Description: Mechanisms to ensure proper citation and referencing of the provided datasets should be provided to ensure credit for the work. This can be done by assigning e.g. DOIs to datasets or create data publications for selected data products in the eLTER context. Reference to the ingested datasets should be given.	
Comments: Related to eLTER-US-D06	
Type: PID, publishing, metadata, Findable, Interoperable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry	

eLTER-US-D11	As a data provider, I want to restrict access to the dataset, so that I can publish data that cannot be made openly available.
Description: There are different types of sensitive data, both GDPR and other types, where access has to be restricted and managed both during and after research. To avoid breaches and leaks the policies and terms of use should be very clear for all parts of the eLTER services. Encryption and pseudonymization services could be considered.	
Comments: similar to eLTER-US-R19 . It would be preferable that access management or data curation should not be left to individual researchers or projects after data publication, but there should be a level of organisation admins that can act as DAC, data owners and right managers.	
Type: access control, user contact, Accessible	

Related components:	
eLTER-US-D12	As a data provider, I need metadata in several languages, so that my national government and public can find the data.
Description: There should be a possibility to have language versions of descriptive metadata. Also multilingual semantic artefacts should be supported. ISO codes should be used for languages.	
Comments: This relates closely to the work within I-ADOPT , but not only, as free text descriptive metadata as well as titles etc should be appreciated as they support both findability and assessment of the data.	
Type: metadata, semantic artefacts, search, Findable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry	
eLTER-US-D13	As a data provider, I have to adhere to the INSPIRE directive, so that my publication is valid.
Description: INSPIRE represents one of many requirements that are posed by both administrative bodies and related infrastructures. An assessment of the most relevant related RI's and architectures should be done on a regular basis to ensure interoperability and adherence to key requirements.	
Comments: The mechanisms and processes used to produce and manage the data management policy in eLTER should be clearly described and implemented. Related to eLTER-US-D14.	
Type: governance, metadata, Interoperable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR	
eLTER-US-D14	As a data provider, I want my data and metadata to be validated, so that it can be reused.
Description: The quality of the metadata in terms of compliance to current standards as well as in terms of completeness and usability of the metadata is important within the network and the emerging eLTER RI. A workflow to check the completeness of the metadata provided needs to be implemented. This applies to the documentation of the sites as well as of the metadata.	
Comments: related to eLTER-US-D13	
Type: ingest, workflows, formats, metadata, Accessible, Interoperable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry, DEIMS-SDR	
eLTER-US-D15	As a data provider, I want to take part in developing workflows and services, so that they can be developed continuously.
Description: The amounts and types of data are growing and the needs are developing. There should be a dynamic empowered community that can respond and assess requirements and solutions. FAIR has to be implemented step by step. Findability should be prioritised.	
Comments: User centric service development and co-development should be implemented systematically across the eLTER services	

Type: user contact, workflows, PID, code repository, code	
Related components: DataLab, gitHub	
eLTER-US-D16	As a data provider, I want to use common provided workflows to ensure quality control and checking on the data prior to data submission.
Description: Standardisation of the quality assessment and control needs to be defined for the eLTER RI to ensure reusability of data. Services should be provided in order to support this task for the data providers. This also includes the tracking of data manipulation and handling during this process.	
Comments: Registration of instruments includes the use of common models to describe these artefacts.	
Type: quality control, provenance, workflow, metadata, semantics, Reusable	
Related components: Digital Asset Registry, DataLab, QC service, prov service	
eLTER-US-D17	As a data provider, I want to register my instruments and get a (persistent identifier (PID) for them, so I can link to them in my documentation.
Description: In order to enable linking of instruments in the data workflows and documentation a registration and documentation of instruments (e.g. sensors, protocols) is needed. Assignment of PIDs to these artefacts is needed.	
Comments:	
Type: instruments, provenance, metadata, PIDs, semantics, Interoperable, Reusable	
Related components: DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset Registry, PID	
eLTER-US-D18	As a data provider, I want to register my site and get a PID for it, so that I can link to it in my dataset description metadata.
Description: In order to enable linking of sites in the data workflows and documentation a registration and documentation of sites (e.g. sites, sensors) is needed. Assignment of PIDs to these artefacts is needed.	
Comments: currently the deims.id is used and should be replaced by a de-referenceable PID (e.g. DataCite DOI)	
Type: provenance, metadata, PIDs, semantics, Interoperable, Reusable	
Related components: DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset Registry, PID	
eLTER-US-D19	As a data provider, I want to track the use of my data.

Description: Tracking of the data use should be tracked via common statistics (e.g. provided by CrossRef). This includes views, downloads, altmetrics, citations etc
Comments: PID services should be chosen so that they can support tracking.
Type: citation, provenance, metadata, PIDs, Findable
Related components: DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset Registry

eLTER-US-D20	As a data provider, I want support in mapping metadata formats in a coherent way, so that the findability and metadata quality is optimal when importing metadata.
Description: Mapping of local metadata elements to a common schema used in the eLTER context should be provided in order to avoid manual interaction when harvesting and ingesting metadata on data sources provided. An evaluation of the metadata quality, e.g. completeness of metadata should be done.	
Comments: Mappings and tools for conversions can enable this.	
Type: workflows, metadata, PID, Interoperable, Reusable	
Related components: DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset Registry	

eLTER-US-D21	As a data provider, I want to publish different versions of my dataset from different stages of the life cycle (raw data, cleaned and validated data and a harmonised data product), so that different use cases are enabled and we get maximal gain from the data.
Description: Different data levels and products should be linked in a coherent and unambiguous way. A normalised terminology and description of data levels should be in place. This also includes clear policies when errors are corrected in the data: how to document this in a coherent way!	
Comments: Provenance tracking, shared workflows and data lifecycle management as well as good PID management will enable this.	
Type: workflows, provenance, metadata, publishing, Interoperable, Reusable	
Related components: DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset Registry	

eLTER-US-D22	As a data provider, I want to link my dataset to sites, so that provenance and format are clear and unambiguous
Description: Information on the sites as the observation context are important to ensure reusability of the data. This information should be linked to the data being generated using persistent identification as part of the provenance tracking.	
Comments: related to eLTER-US-D18	
Type: sites, provenance, metadata, PID, semantics, Reusable	
Related components: DEIMS-SDR, Digital Asset Registry	

8.5.3 Other Stakeholders

eLTER-US-U01	As a user, I want to visualise data (spatial and time series) of interest for visual inspection of the data.
Description: Visualisation tools are needed to study and assess data as well as make them more accessible for the general public (i.e. open).	
Comments: all users (incl. policy makers, general public). Related to eLTER-US-R03	
Type: data, visualisation, Interoperable, Reusable	
Related components:	

8.6 ICT Requirements Mapping to ENVRI-RM

Table 20: Mapping of ENVRI-RM to eLTER User Stories

ENVRI RM requirements		eLTER requirement	Description
A	Data Acquisition		
A.5	Configuration logging	eLTER-US-R02	
A.7	Parameter data visualisation	- missing -	
A.8	Real-Time Parameter/Data Visualisation	- missing -	
A.9	Process control	- missing -	
A.4	Instrument access	- missing -	
A.3	Instrument Calibration	- missing -	
A.1	Instrument Integration	- missing -	
A.2	Instrument Configuration	- missing -	
A.6	Instrument monitoring	- missing -	
A.10	Data collection	eLTER-US-R02, eLTER-US-D04, eLTER-US-R01, eLTER-US-D08"	
A.12	Data Sampling	- missing -	
A.11	Real-Time Data Collection	- missing -	
A.13	Noise Reduction	- missing -	
A.14	Data Transmission	- missing -	
A.16	Data Transmission Monitoring	- missing -	
A.15	Real-Time Data Transmission	- missing -	
B.	Data curation		
B.7	Workflow Enactment	eLTER-US-D16	
B.1	Data Quality Checking	eLTER-US-D14	
B.2	Data Quality verification	eLTER-US-D14	
B.8	Data Storage & Preservation	eLTER-US-R02, eLTER-US-D03, eLTER-US-D04, eLTER-US-R01	
B.4	Data Cataloguing	eLTER-US-R02, eLTER-US-D05	
B.5	Data Product Generation	eLTER-US-R02, eLTER-US-D02	eLTER-US-D02: "Access to common protocols" not exactly B.5 issue, but it is close
B.3	Data Identification	eLTER-US-R17	eLTER-US-R17 is only about linking to results. It is not an exact match
B.6	Data Versioning	eLTER-US-D21, eLTER-US-R06	
B.9	Data Replication	- missing -	
B.10	Replica synchronization	- missing -	
C.	Data Publishing	eLTER-US-R11, eLTER-US-R16	

ENVRI RM requirements		eLTER requirement	Description
C.10	Data Compression	- missing -	
C.4	Metadata Harvesting	- missing -	
C.13	Semantic Harmonisation	eLTER-US-R09, eLTER-US-D07	eLTER-US-D07 not exactly C.13, but close
C.9	Data conversion	- missing -	Data conversions on publishing phase not discussed in user stories
C.2	Resources Annotation	- missing -	
C.3	Data Annotation	- missing -	
C.5	Resource registration	eLTER-US-D17	
C.8	Sensor registration	eLTER-US-D17	
C.7	Identifier registration	- missing -	
C.6	Metadata registration	- missing -	
C.1	Access control		
C.11	Data publication	eLTER-US-R05	eLTER-US-R05 Publication with provenance metadata; Creation and publication of compiled dataset not in ENVRI RM
C.15	Data visualisation	- missing -	
C.14	Data discovery and access	eLTER-US-R20	
C.12	Data citation	eLTER-US-D10	
D.	Data Processing		
D.8	Service naming	- missing -	
D.6	Scientific workflow enactment	eLTER-US-R02	
D.7	Scientific visualisation	- missing -	
D.9	Data processing control	- missing -	
D.10	Data processing monitoring	- missing -	
D.5	Scientific modelling and simulation	- missing -	
D.4	Data extraction	- missing -	
D.3	Data mining	- missing -	
D.2	Data analysis	- missing -	
D.1	Data assimilation	- missing -	
E.	Data Use		
E.6	Interactive visualisation	eLTER-US-U01	
E.5	Instant messaging	eLTER-US-R08	eLTER-US-R08 is not exactly about instant messaging, but it is rather close
E.7	Event notification	- missing -	
E.4	User registration	eLTER-US-R19	
E.1	Authentication	eLTER-US-R19, eLTER-US-D11	
E.2	Authorization	eLTER-US-R19, eLTER-US-D11	
E.3	Accounting	eLTER-US-D19	

Table 21: eLTER User Stories not corresponding to function ENVRI RM

eLTER US Nr	Description	Comment
eLTER-US-D01	As a data provider, I need support with creating a good data management plan, so that all data is compliant, interoperable and of good quality.	Support not in ENVRI RM
eLTER-US-D02	As a data provider, I want to have access to common protocols, so that datasets are harmonized as early as possible in the data lifecycle.	This is not exactly B.5 issue, but close
eLTER-US-D06	As a data provider, I want to export metadata, so that I don't have to type or copy-paste each value manually.	Metadata export not in ENVRI RM. Should perhaps be under "Data discovery and access"
eLTER-US-D09	As a data provider, I want to have a rich data model, so that I can express the organization of my datasets in a clear way.	Not mentioned in ENVRI. Closest possibility would be B.8 Data Storage & Preservation
eLTER-US-D12	As a data provider, I need metadata in several languages, so that my national government and public can find the data	Language not discussed in ENVRI model. Perhaps it should be a functionality under B.8 Data Storage & Preservation
eLTER-US-D13	As a data provider, I have to adhere to the INSPIRE directive, so that my publication is valid.	What exactly are the requirements of the Inspire directive ?
eLTER-US-D15	As a data provider, I want to take part in developing workflows and services, so that they can be developed continuously.	Not in ENVRI RM.
eLTER-US-D18	As a data provider, I want to register my site and get a PID for it, so that I can link to it in my dataset description metadata.	Not in ENVRI RM. Should be in "Data Acquisition"
eLTER-US-D20	As a data provider, I want support in mapping metadata formats in a coherent way, so that the findability and metadata quality is optimal when importing metadata.	Such a support feature is not in ENVRI RM functions
eLTER-US-R03	As a researcher I want to compare datasets, so that I can assess them.	No in ENVRI RM as such
eLTER-US-R04	As a researcher I want to do data conversions into recommended formats, so that I can use eLTER tools.	This function is in ENVRI RM, but it is under "Data publishing". Manual data processing using predefined tools is not described clearly in ENVRI RM
eLTER-US-R07	As a researcher I want to manage different versions of my code, so that I can track errors.	Software development is not in ENVRI RM. This idea would be worth evaluating further !
eLTER-US-R08	As a researcher I want to contact the data provider, so that I can validate the suitability of the dataset for my research.	Not exactl E.5 Instant messaging, but close
eLTER-US-R10	As a researcher I want to contact the service provider, to apply for more resources.	Not in ENVRI RM. This is actually IT service management issue. In FitSM terminology, the end user should start "Incident management and Request fulfillment" process.
eLTER-US-R12	As a researcher I want training, so that I can use the tools efficiently.	Training activities are not in ENVRI RM
eLTER-US-R13	As a researcher I need support with optimizing my code, so that I can be as fast as the next group.	Not in ENVRI RM
eLTER-US-R14	As a researcher I want to manage my workflows and share them, so that I get more citations	Is sharing same as publishing or is sharing only to some known persons/group ? This is not exactly on ENVRI RM, but a new registered dataset containing a workflow could be created. What kind of identifier

eLTER-US Nr	Description	Comment
		would be needed for registered workflows ? How permanent we should consider them to be ?
eLTER-US-R15	As a researcher I want documentation to be automatic when possible, so that the metadata and links are standardized	This is a feature or principle supported by at least "Data Acquisition" and "Data Use" functions
eLTER-US-R17	As a researcher I want to link my outputs, so that my research is reproducible.	This is not only about having a link to data, but it is also about possibility to make relations between datasets
eLTER-US-R18	As a researcher I want to control how my data is stored, so that I can influence the retention time.	This "storage policy" control, should be under " B.8 Data Storage & Preservation. Now the focus is only on long term storage. Policy based short and medium term storage is not discussed.

< End of document >

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